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Evaluation of the Ports, Past & Present Programme

Final report June 2023

Ports, Past and Present
Calafort, Inniu agus Inné
Porthladdoedd, Ddoe a Heddiw

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List of abbreviations

CAWCS	Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies
DMO	Destination Management Organisation
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
IMDO	Irish Maritime Development Office
PPP	Ports, Past & Present
UCC	University College Cork
UKSPF	UK Shared Prosperity Fund
UWTSD	University of Wales Trinity St. David's
WCC	Wexford County Council
WEFO	Welsh European Funding Office
WIMD	Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation

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Executive Summary

This is the final evaluation report for Ports, Past and Present, a multi-institutional project about the five Irish Sea ports of Dublin Port and Rosslare in Ireland and Fishguard, Holyhead and Pembroke Dock in Wales. It has been conducted by Wavehill on behalf of University College Cork, the commissioning body for the operation. Wavehill were commissioned in Spring 2021 to undertake this work.

About the project

Ports, Past and Present is a cross-border action between Higher Education Institutions in Wales and the Republic of Ireland. It has been funded by the European Regional Development Fund through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme, managed by the Welsh European Funding Office (WEFO), under the Priority Axis 3: 'Cultural & Natural Resources and Heritage'. The aim was to stimulate economic growth by utilising the assets, enhancing the natural and cultural environment and increasing the attractiveness of the coastal communities in the programme area as places to visit. A key focus was on supporting the diversification the tourism sector to increase visitor numbers to coastal communities and the 'result indicator' for the priority is the total number of overseas visitors to the coastal communities of the Programme area. The aim was to create a new joint and shared future for five port towns in the Irish Sea basin, based on a deeper understanding of their past. The ports are Rosslare, Dublin Port, Fishguard, Holyhead and Pembroke Dock. The operation started in May 2019 and runs until July 2023.

Project delivery

The operation was launched in 2020 following a longer than anticipated period of design and development. It has not only been directly impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent restrictions imposed in Wales and Ireland, but also by the strict application of these restrictions in the academic institutions and local authority partners leading the delivery. These restrictions have curtailed the efforts to physically engage local communities across the five port towns and as such impacted the progress made across all the work packages. It has directly impacted on ferry passenger numbers and as such visitor volumes connected to each port. The operation has also been influenced by the progress of Brexit negotiations and more recently the refugee crisis caused by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Feedback from staff and contractors has highlighted satisfaction with the partnership working and governance arrangements for the operation. The Stakeholder Advisory Group was cited as providing valuable and timely guidance and support. Staff turnover has created challenges to maintaining delivery momentum and partnership working with the level of turnover associated with the use of fixed-term contracts. However the Programme Board have acted to recruit to posts to ensure that the contracted deliverables are achieved. Greater coordination with other cross-border initiatives should have taken place at an earlier stage to avoid any duplication of effort in the creation of tourism and business networks and to align marketing and communication activities.

Whilst the Project Team did attempt to coordinate with the other Ireland-Wales Interreg operations, including instigating a series of collaborative meetings facilitated by Planed, a Pembrokeshire community development organisation, the ability to collaborate across operations was limited due to time and capacity constraints. An important learning point for the design of future operations is the inclusion of actions that seek to identify and develop relations with operations with shared interests and goals. With hindsight, inclusion at the design stage of the various Ireland-Wales Interreg operations may have delivered operational efficiencies, avoided duplication of effort, and enabled pooling of resources where possible.

Project achievements

Creative connections

The participatory approach to delivering the creative connections work packages has provided opportunities for local communities to engage in the creative process to build a sense of pride and ownership. The outputs from this work package have the potential to attract visitors, increase dwell time and improve visitor experience. However, without a clear destination marketing campaign, which was not incorporated into the design of the operation, the visibility of these may be low and they will not realise their potential.

Documentary Films

Developing the content for the documentary films has enabled the operation to engage and involve a range of stakeholders, supported by extensive research by the academic teams at University College Cork and Aberystwyth University as well as the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies in Wales. Five documentary films were launched between June and October 2022 and have to date achieved 15,153 combined views. The intellectual property rights for the videos resides with the operation and its institutions but are required to be non-commercial in their use. This means that the videos can be reproduced and reused if they are attributed. This opens the prospects of the documentary films anchoring any future destination marketing campaigns to raise the profile of the heritage of the ports and encourage growth in visitor numbers.

Bringing the past to life

Port Fest Events have provided opportunities to showcase the work of the operation in covering and promoting tourism in the often underappreciated ports. Opportunities to integrate and embed the work of the operation with other cultural festivals and events has also been realised. A total of 90 events and activities have been delivered by the operation, which has engaged at least 14,806 audience members and participants. Collectively they demonstrate the creative diversity of the operation and as a result wide appeal. They have been used to generate connections, explore collaboration opportunities, gather insight and data to inform creative and academic outputs and build momentum to raise the profile of the port stories. Those attending the events and activities agreed that their experiences had positively affected their sense of place and local identity and made them feel more connected to the other coastal port communities in the Irish Sea.

The Port Places App

The development and launch of the Port Places App forms one of the key deliverables for the operation and one that has perhaps the most significance for the operation's legacy. To date 444 users have downloaded the app, which suggests that further work is required if this tool is to realise its potential. The Project Team have identified an 'app champion' in each of the port towns to promote the app and encourage its use, and these are now in place in all 5 ports.

Tourism Network

The creation of a self-sustaining tourism network was one of the key deliverables for the operation. Whilst attendances at some network events have so far been lower than hoped for, they do form part of a longer-term activity to connect and activate local businesses to support a process of raising the profile of the ports and attracting tourism. The operation has made efforts throughout to showcase port businesses and their role in port communities. This has been delivered through a combination of research and creative activities, most notably the stories gathered from businesses and local communities.

Feedback from some stakeholders has highlighted wider, external influences that impact on the ability of the ports to realise their potential and build on the momentum delivered by Ports, Past and Present. The most prominent was the current ferry timetables between Wales and Ireland but also the lack of accommodation offer and transport connectivity affecting the ports.

Communication and dissemination

Between the 1st June 2020 and 4th May 2023 the website received visits from 37,667 users, over 53,025 sessions and involving 118,010 page views. The 8 documentary films produced have combined recorded 30,352 views, with an average of 316 views per film. Around one in seven of the documentary films produced have recorded over 500 views. The various social media channels have also worked to extend the reach of the operation.

Outcomes and impacts

The operation has engaged a wide range of stakeholders with influence and interests across local heritage and community-based regeneration. Approaching two thirds of stakeholders rated their town or port's heritage as either extremely or very important to their business or organization. This demonstrates that the operation has connected with a stakeholder group who realise the potential to draw on the heritage value of each of the ports and the cross-border story to deliver social and economic outcomes. Around four in ten stakeholders said that the amount of time tourists spent within their area had increased over the past year. It is not possible to accurately determine the extent to which the operation has influenced the number of, and time spent by tourists.

Stakeholders report that Ports, Past and Present has raised the visibility of their local area's heritage in both the eyes of locals and tourists. Just over a fifth of stakeholders reported that they did not have enough information to determine any change in the importance of heritage within their local area. This highlights the potential role moving forward of the Tourism Network established by the operation as a forum to monitor and discuss the role of heritage in the local tourism offer.

Cross-cutting themes

Ports, Past & Present has undertaken a range of activities to ensure compliance with the Sustainable Development CCT including sustainable transport initiatives, the use of green procurement processes and incorporation of environmental issues and themes within creative commissions.

Delivery of the operation has contributed towards efforts to tackle poverty and social exclusion, in particular by ensuring reach of community engagement activities to disadvantaged or underrepresented groups. It has also helped to build capacity and skills both within port communities and working collaboratively with schools and youth groups. The operation has taken forward a range of actions to ensure compliance with the equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming strategic aims, overseen by an Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming Champion. Combined, the operation has provided a positive contribution to several goals for The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015.

Legacy and sustainability

There is a strong desire from stakeholders for the operation to establish a legacy vehicle to build on or sustain the momentum achieved through its delivery to date. Realising the potential for the history, heritage and connections between the five ports to contribute to future growth in visitor numbers and the tourism economy requires many of the outputs of the operation to be taken-up, viewed, reused and repurposed. There is a danger that without coordination there will be unnecessary duplication of effort across the Interreg cross-border projects and opportunities for alignment will be missed.

The future funding position is unclear given each nation will now proceed with different funding regimes. However, in principle, the aspirations and objectives of the operation continue to align with those of both Interreg and UKSPF. The Ireland-Wales shared statement and joint action plan for 2021 to 2025 sets out 6 areas of cooperation, which includes Trade and Tourism and Culture, Language and Heritage and a commitment to initiate exploratory discussions to foster potential cooperation and collaboration between their respective tourism agencies. This has direct relevance for the legacy of Ports, Past and Present.

Recommendations

A small number of recommendations are provided below for consideration by the Programme Board.

1. Assess options and funding to establish a legacy vehicle to build on the momentum developed by the operation across the five ports.
2. Consider resourcing a destination marketing campaign which draws on the creative output and stories captured by the operation and uses them to promote the ports as destinations.
3. Connect the Tourism Networks more explicitly to respective Destination Management Organisations, tour operators and local business bodies to explore opportunities and barriers to driving visitor numbers and dwell time across the ports.
4. Ensure that opportunities to embed heritage and the work of Ports, Past and Present into future capital programmes across each of the ports are realised and assess the potential to include meaningful Corporate Social Responsibility elements in future contracts with port and ferry companies to address the lack of voluntary engagement from the commercial sectors with the Irish Sea Port communities.

1. Introduction

This is the final evaluation report for Ports, Past and Present (operation), a multi-institutional project (referred to as an ‘operation’ for the remainder of this report in line with the terminology used by the funder) about the five Irish Sea ports of Dublin Port and Rosslare in Ireland and Fishguard, Holyhead and Pembroke Dock in Wales. It has been conducted by Wavehill on behalf of University College Cork (UCC), the commissioning body for the operation. Wavehill were commissioned in Spring 2021 to undertake this work.

1.1 About the project

Ports, Past and Present is a cross-border action between Higher Education Institutions in Wales and the Republic of Ireland, including University College Cork (UCC), Aberystwyth University, the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies (CAWCS)/University of Wales Trinity St. David (UWTSD) alongside local authority, Wexford County Council (WCC), in the Republic of Ireland.

It is funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme, managed by the Welsh European Funding Office (WEFO). More specifically, the operation is funded under Priority Axis 3 of the Programme: ‘Cultural & Natural Resources and Heritage’. The aim is to stimulate economic growth by utilising the assets, enhancing the natural and cultural environment and increasing the attractiveness of the coastal communities in the programme area as places to visit. A key focus is on supporting the **diversification the tourism sector to increase visitor numbers to coastal communities and the ‘result indicator’ for the priority is the total number of overseas visitors to the coastal communities** of the Programme area.¹

The operation comprises a partnership across higher education and local government and involves a broad range of stakeholders and beneficiaries. The operation aims to increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic and particularly tourist growth.

The aim was to create a new joint and shared future for five port towns in the Irish Sea basin, based on a deeper understanding of their past. The ports are Rosslare, Dublin Port, Fishguard, Holyhead and Pembroke Dock. The operation started in May 2019 and runs until July 2023.

There are existing links between the five sea-ports as a result of the current passenger routes, and a cross-border tourism network will be established to link together economic, political, cultural and community actors.

¹ [Ireland Wales Indicator definitions](#)

In particular, the following routes are of interest because they illustrate the existing cross-border cultural and business links:

- Rosslare Harbour and Fishguard
- Rosslare Harbour and Pembroke Dock
- Dublin and Holyhead

A key aim of the operation was to inform and shape the long-term heritage tourism strategies of the five port communities and their surrounding areas. The operation aimed to achieve this through several key strategies and mechanisms linked to the deliverables of the operation.

First, the operation would **produce deliverables** that aim to inform regional and local tourism strategies beyond the life of the programme. This included undertaking heritage interpretation activities including the generation of information boards, creative works, films, the shaping of digital displays, and other strategies.

Second, the team would **work closely with local stakeholders** (in local authorities, local museums and heritage groups, local schools and communities) to involve them in the generation and dissemination of the port history and heritage. This was expected to generate a long-term interest amongst local groups and individuals which would empower them to explore these histories further, generating a long-term 'local' concern with the heritage of the five ports.

The third aim was to **set up a self-sustaining tourism network**. It was hoped that, after the programme's closure in 2023, this network would continue to be fostered and advanced by key stakeholders (whether local chambers of commerce, local authorities, or local business leaders). The operation has ensured that any media associated with the tourism network (for example websites) are hosted on freely accessible sites, and a clear strategy developed to minimise the risk of these failing in the future. In providing a forum for local businesses to share experiences of tourism in the port towns, new employment opportunities are expected to emerge as the potential growth areas for port-based heritage tourism become apparent.

Fourth, it was hoped that the **wider economic benefits** of the operation would snowball, with the increasing popularity of Wales and Ireland as cruise destinations, and the potential for ferry passengers to extend their stay in the ports or to use their time in ports in different ways, especially prior to departure.

1.2 Aims and objectives

Objective: To sustainably realise the potential of natural and cultural assets in increasing visitor numbers to coastal communities of the programme area.

Programme Result Indicator: Total number of overseas visitors to the coastal communities of the Programme area.

1.3 Output Indicators

Number of new tourism networks promoting cultural, natural or heritage assets: 2.

Number of coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism: 5.

Employment increase in supported enterprises: 2 FTE roles.

1.4 Operation work packages

The operation of PPP has been delivered across the following six work packages:

Work Package 1: Project management and governance.

Work Package 2: Creative connections. Twelve commissions of £5,000 each to allow twelve creative practitioners to work with community groups on creative projects exploring the history and heritage of the five port towns and the journeys made across the Irish Sea.

Work Package 3: Documentary films. The operation to commission, provide some content for and advise on five short documentary films exploring the history and stories of the five ports with their associated sea crossings.

Work Package 4: Bringing the past to life. This WP has responsibility for providing accessible pathways to new interpretations of the maritime past by developing visualisations (story maps, geolocated maps, displays across the five sites) of past sea crossings and the history of the ports. These will be available via mobile apps that can be downloaded before, during and after travel and which will give depth and richness to the experience of sea crossings.

Work Package 5: Community events and knowledge exchange.

Work Package 6: Communication and dissemination. WP6 communicates the work and value proposition of PPP.

1.5 Purpose of Research and Background

The purpose of the external evaluation was to support measurement of the operation's progress against agreed deliverables. Initial evaluation was used to establish the baseline data that demonstrates the need for the operation and from which progress towards the operation's objectives could be assessed. The end-of-operation evaluation, which this report represents, is used to assess and understand the impact of the operation. The evaluation has both identified and utilised existing datasets to inform the research and fill in information gaps in those datasets. The evaluation has also considered and accounted for the global COVID-19 pandemic and its likely disturbance of prior trends in existing datasets and influence and impact on the delivery and future prospects for the operation.

It should be noted that the port towns vary in character, and research may vary as a result. 'Port towns' can refer to a wider radius than the borders of the town itself, and may refer to the general local area, depending on the location.

The operation's Monitoring and Evaluation Plan outlined an intention to establish a baseline position for each of the five ports for tourist numbers, visitor dwell time and the amount of money they spend. This would enable growth in visitor numbers and spend to be monitored to enable calculations on the contribution that the operation has made to local economies. However, as highlighted in the scoping work of the operation, whilst existing passenger data provides information on the number of people passing through ports, they do not provide more detailed information about dwell time (including overnight stays), the profile of visitors and spend.

As outlined in this report, these gaps persist, creating challenges in quantifying the impact of the operation. It has not been within the remit or budget of the operation nor the commissioned evaluation to put in place systems to capture this data. This is an area for consideration as part of any onward legacy discussions (see later section of this report).

The evaluation team has used a mixed-methods approach. This report is based on the following:

- Review of relevant policy and research (Wales and Ireland), providing context for the delivery of the operation;
- Review of all project documentation including Delivery Plans, Internal Evaluation Reports, Newsletters, event and activity feedback data and social media data;
- Qualitative interviews with 8 Project Team members, 1 Contractors and 21 Stakeholders;
- Baseline survey (105 responses) and Follow-up Survey (69 responses); and
- Review of Work Package outputs, including creative outputs, documentary films, the Port Places App, Heritage Tours and Heritage Stories (being retained within the Digital Repository of Ireland and People's Collection Wales)

Research tools used for this final phase of the evaluation are provided in the [Appendices](#).

1.6 Rationale

Ports play a vital role in the economy of Ireland and Wales, providing employment while facilitating trade and creating vital lines of connection between and across borders. Many port towns are however sites of economic deprivation, places through which visitors pass through rather than stop in. Coastal communities around port towns depend on the movement of people and goods but, as with visitors, some may not be deeply aware of the histories and stories attached to the ports, while others may not have the tools to engagingly share their heritage.

In both Ireland and Wales, Brexit is having an impact on the geographies of mobility through ports, as recognised by the 2017 Welsh Senedd committee inquiry report on the potential impact of Brexit on Welsh ports.² These concerns largely related to questions around a hard border and customs infrastructure but also that the role of port towns is under threat.

The ports forming part of the operation are sites of economic disadvantage. The 2014 Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation³ (WIMD), the most recent at the time of the project's development, showed that areas of two of the three port towns are some of the most deprived in Wales. In the Republic of Ireland, Wexford has the 3rd highest rate of unemployed people in all local authorities; and, although Dublin Port is the largest and busiest Irish port in the Irish port sector, the population of the Dublin Port area is ageing faster than the national average.

The 2016 Pobal HP Deprivation Index⁴ for the Republic of Ireland, which synthesises data on unemployment, low educational attainment, one-parent families, ageing and social housing around a State average of zero, reveals deprivation i.e. negative values in the Irish port towns too. There is an extensive cluster of disadvantaged neighbourhoods in and around Rosslare Harbour with values below -10, which reach their nadir in the harbour area (-15). While the picture is more complex around Dublin Port, affluent areas are juxtaposed with some of the city centre's 'very disadvantaged' neighbourhoods including Sheriff St. Lwr. (-21 to -27) and Summerhill Parade (-21 to -24).

1.7 Operation Management

UCC has been the lead beneficiary with Aberystwyth University, CAWCS/UWTSD and Wexford County Council as joint beneficiaries. Between them they have supplied the skills of academics, researchers, project management and project delivery staff. (17 posts of varying responsibility and seniority, as per business plan). As per Figure 1.1 over page, Operational Governance has been structured via:

- A Programme Board
- A UCC Project Management and Monitoring Board
- Stakeholder Advisory Group (Membership of 10)
- Internal reporting

As outlined in this report, several local and regional stakeholders of varying size have been involved with the operation to varying degrees, for example, museums, local businesses and port authorities.

² [Inquiry into the implications of Brexit for Welsh ports \(senedd.wales\)](https://www.senedd.wales)

³ View [Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation](#)

⁴ View [Pobal Deprivation Indices](#)

Figure 1.1 Operational Governance Structure

1.8 Headline Operation Costs and co-financing

The operation is funded by the ERDF through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme, running from May 2019 to July 2023. The expenditure allocated to the operation is as below:

EXPENDITURE	€ TOTAL
Staff costs	2,286,510
Non-staff costs	527,397
15% flat rate	355,061
TOTAL	€3,168,968

Funded by: ERDF @ 80%	2,535,174
Indirect costs	355,06
Match funding @ 20%	643,308
TOTAL	€3,178,482

1.9 Activities

During the lifetime of the operation, it was intended to focus on the following goals and related outputs:

- Develop a better understanding of the history of the five port towns to underpin the activities/outputs and heritage-led regeneration. Documentary and oral history

research into the maritime and coastal history of the port towns, including generating visual materials.

- Work with port communities will help to generate more heritage-related stories, develop skills and ensure longer-term outcomes and impact. Community workshops and events that share and disseminate knowledge of cultural heritage and improve skills relating to social media use in the promotion of heritage-related tourism.
- Creative responses across a range of media will attract visitors to spend more time/money in ports and will create a structured set of experiences for them. Commissioning creative engagements with cultural heritage to shape lasting cultural legacies; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns.
- Films will publicise ports' heritage and encourage visitors and operators to plan to spend more time and money in port towns. Commissioning documentary films that showcase stories and voices from the coastal communities; to be developed in consultation with communities in the port towns.
- Graphic displays of port history will structure guided walks around the ports (including key heritage sites and commissioned artwork). Graphic displays of cultural heritage located in the ports.
- Heritage-related apps can attract new visitors to the ports and structure their touristic experience of the ports. Digital visualisations of past sea crossings and the history of the ports.

1.10 Programme logic model

The activities undertaken by the operation have been underpinned by a logic model (Figure 1.1 over page) which maps out the relationship between the underlying challenge for the project, the activities undertaken to address the challenge, and the various outputs, outcomes/deliverables and impacts that derive from these activities. The model highlights the logic or assumptions that underpin the relationships between various components of the logic model. These are explored in this evaluation report along with an assessment against the ultimate goal/impact for Ports, Past & Present.⁵

⁵ Ports Past and Present. Monitoring and Evaluation Plan. Version 3.

Figure 1.1 Programme logic model

1.11 Output Indicators (Results)

New tourism network established. Examples may include: Evidence of a dedicated network web-site; evidence of cross-border events organised; cross-border marketing plans and initiatives. A tourism network will help to draw together organisations and businesses in Ireland and Wales concerned with heritage tourism. This new cross-border network will allow organisations and businesses to exploit synergies (for example joint marketing of activities).

Engaging and linking together five coastal communities around cultural and heritage tourism. Examples may include: evidence of engagement with community stakeholders and groups; evidence of outputs targeted at local communities. Working with and bringing together the five coastal communities will help to generate more heritage-related stories, develop skills, explore synergies and ensure longer-term outcomes and impact.

The outputs will lead to an **increased dwell time in ports, with increased tourist spend and a greater demand for local services – leading to job creation.**

Two FTE jobs created in supported enterprises on the basis of the outputs. This will be evidenced by self-declaration by Supported Enterprises, including details of the posts created, statement on the link to ERDF funding, details of salary band, and gender of post-holder. The 'Self-declaration' form will be forwarded to WEFO for approval.

Ports Past and Present Indicators	Status
Number of new tourism networks promoting cultural, natural or heritage assets: 2.	Achieved
Number of coastal communities participating in cross-border cooperation around cultural, natural or heritage tourism: 5.	Achieved
Employment increase in supported enterprises: 2 FTE roles.	Not Achieved

1.12 Longer-Term Outcomes/Impact

A greater awareness among port communities of their (shared) heritage, and an increased amount of tourist dwell time and spend based on this heritage. The community and business benefits of tourism will be embedded in the port communities and will be supported by the tourism network.

1.12.1 Project Delivery

Work Package 1: Operation Management and Governance - Predicted longer-term benefits: the creation of a team of individuals possessing extensive knowledge and experience of heritage-led development in port settlements; the creation of a template of various activities that could be used to implement the heritage-led redevelopment of port settlements elsewhere.

Work Package 2: Creative Connections - Predicted longer-term benefits: the **creation of a sustained and heightened interest in heritage in the five port settlements** (among community groups and SMEs); the **creation of tourism networks** that will provide the basis for ongoing artistic and heritage-related collaboration between the five port settlements; the commissioning of **permanent creative works** in the five port settlements; creative artwork and community-led heritage engagement activities leading to additional time and money spent by tourists and travellers.

Work Package 3: Producing Documentary Films - Predicted longer-term benefits: **documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports** on display in the ports themselves (as part of an increased dwell time for travellers); documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports shown on ferries (to increase dwell time on future visits); documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports displayed on ferry-booking websites (allowing ferry travellers to increase the time they spend in ports); documentary films commemorating the heritage of the ports on display on cruise websites/ships (promoting bespoke walking tours of the heritage of the port settlements).

Work Package 4: Bringing the Past to Life - Predicted longer-term benefits: a series of **permanent display boards located in the port settlements**, forming part of a heritage 'trail' around the port settlements; websites, the creation of a dedicated app, and other social media content established and maintained by community groups in order to promote the heritage of the port settlements; display boards and website content encouraging ferry travellers and cruise tourists to view the port settlements as tourist destinations in their own right.

Work Package 5: Community events and knowledge exchange - Predicted longer-term benefits: the **creation of a sustained and heightened interest in heritage in the five port settlements** (among community groups and SMEs); an **increased capacity within community and heritage groups to promote the heritage of port towns** (tours, flyers, social media, talks etc); the creation of tourism networks that will provide the basis for ongoing artistic and heritage-related knowledge exchange between the five port settlements.

Work Package 6: Communication and dissemination - Predicted longer-term benefits: the production of a **series of policy and practitioner related outputs outlining the use of heritage-led regeneration in port communities**; websites on heritage-led regeneration in port settlements maintained and updated by community groups and the Port Places App.

1.12.2 Envisaged impacts

It was hoped that the operation would result in a range of impacts for the ports and port communities, including:

- Coastal communities enjoy an increased awareness of their cultural heritage and develop new opportunities for heritage tourism.
- Port towns become 'stopping places' and 'spending places' rather than just 'through places' for tourists, with an increase in tourism-related employment
- Tourism Networks are formed between twinned Irish and Welsh ports, linking local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish Sea.
- Producing tangible heritage deliverables that will exist beyond the life of the programme.
- Work closely with relevant local stakeholders to engage them with their local culture, nature and heritage so that they feel a sense of ownership going forward.
- To create a self-sustaining tourism network that will continue to work effectively after the programme ends in 2023. The operation will give the network the tools needed to achieve this, which in turn will lead to new employment opportunities.
- That overall tourism to the two countries will increase, and in particular dwell time in the five port towns will be extended due to the enhanced heritage visitor experiences.
- Achievements will be assessed against set deliverables including the number of new tourism networks created, number of coastal communities participating, number of new jobs created and the total number of overseas visitors to the five identified areas.

2. Context of the port communities

The operation includes five port towns around the Irish Sea. We set the context for these locations below, an understanding of which is important in assessing the progress made across the different work packages and ultimately the prospects for Ports, Past and Present achieving its ultimate aim.

2.1 Fishguard

Fishguard (Abergwaun in Welsh) is a town in North Pembrokeshire, Wales, on the Irish Sea. The English name derives from Norse while the Welsh means ‘mouth of the River Gwaun’. Ferries cross between the harbour and Rosslare Harbour in the Republic of Ireland, while several trains arrive per day from south Wales cities, including Cardiff and Swansea. The town is linked by the A40 southwards to Haverfordwest and the A487 towards coastal towns to the north.

According to population estimates in 2020, the population of Fishguard is 3,480.⁶ The three main employment sectors for the residents of Fishguard are wholesale and retail trade for example repair of motor vehicles, human health and social work activities, and construction. According to WIMD, North West Fishguard is in the 20-30% of most deprived areas of Wales for employment and also for education.

The town’s population is generally older, the largest population age in Fishguard is 60-69 followed by 70-79 years of age. Only 62.1% of people in Fishguard are economically active and only 55% of people are in employment. Of the economically inactive, 21.6% of Fishguard’s population are retired.⁷ Although Fishguard and the surrounding area was the site of a medieval battle which led to Tudor control of Pembrokeshire in the late eleventh century, the area’s main claim to fame is as **the site of the last attempted invasion of Great Britain**, when Napoleonic French forces landed in 1797 but were subdued by locals. Aviation history is also promoted locally, as the site of the first sea crossing from Wales to Ireland in 1912.

2.2 Pembroke Dock

Pembroke Dock (Doc Penfro in Welsh) is a town in southern Pembrokeshire, part of the Milford Haven waterway on the Welsh west coast. The town developed around its Royal Naval Shipbuilding Dockyard which was built in 1814.

⁶ [Fishguard \(Pembrokeshire, Wales / Cymru, United Kingdom\) - Population Statistics, Charts, Map, Location, Weather and Web Information \(citypopulation.de\)](#)

⁷ <https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/reports/localarea?compare=W37000036>

Around 260 ships were built in the dockyard between the opening of the yard and its closure more than a hundred years later in 1926. Ships built at Pembroke Dock were used to transport Victorian royalty around the British Empire. Including five Royal Yachts for Queen Victoria. Pembroke Dock later became a base for 'flying ships', playing a major role in World War Two and the Atlantic Ocean.

According to population estimates in 2020, the population for Pembroke Dock is 9,747. The largest population group in Pembroke Dock is between the ages of 50-59 followed by 60-69 years of age, suggesting an aging population. The Llanion 1 ward in Pembroke Dock is in the top 10% of most deprived areas in Wales for income and employment. Central Pembroke Dock and Monkton are also in the 20% most deprived areas in Wales for income, employment, health, and community health.⁸

The main sources of employment for residents in Pembroke Dock are wholesale and retail trade for example repair of motor vehicles, human health and social work activities, and construction.⁹ Other key employers in Pembroke Dock are Valero and nearby oil refineries. Like Fishguard, ferries regularly travel from Pembroke Dock to Rosslare Harbour in the Republic of Ireland. Pembroke Dock has train links to Swansea and Cardiff, and a daily direct train in both directions to London Paddington. By road, the town is reached on the A477 to St Clears, which joins the A40 going eastwards to Carmarthen and the M4.

2.3 Holyhead

Holyhead (Caergybi in Welsh) is on Holy Island, which is now attached by bridge to the larger Isle of Anglesey (Ynys Mon). The location was inhabited in Neolithic times, was the site of a fourth century Roman fort and a sixth century monastery from Saint Cybi, after whom the town's Welsh language name is taken.

The town became the recognized departure point for Ireland, following the 1801 Union; the building of Thomas Telford's A5 road and the link with Chester railway in 1844 strengthening the town's development, as did the new breakwater, completed in 1873. Holyhead is the site for ferry crossings across the Irish Sea to Dublin. The train station is the terminus for direct train services eastwards to Chester, Birmingham, and London, and to the Welsh capital, Cardiff. The town is the end of the A5 and A55 roads towards the English Midlands and the North Wales Expressway towards Chester and Liverpool respectively.

⁸ View [Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation 2019](#)

⁹ [Local Area Report for areas in England and Wales - Nomis \(nomisweb.co.uk\)](#)

According to population estimates in 2020, the population for Holyhead is 12,060, making it the largest town in Anglesey.¹⁰ 32% of residents have no qualifications and 66.5% either don't have qualifications or only have level 2 qualifications.¹¹ Only 53% of residents are in employment.¹² 26% of Holyhead's population is estimated to be income deprived.¹³

According to the WIMD, the central Holyhead ward is in the 10% of most deprived areas in Wales¹⁴ including for income, employment, and community safety. Other industries traditionally associated with the area include Anglesey Aluminium, which closed in 2009, and Wylfa nuclear power plant at Cemaes Bay.

2.4 Rosslare Harbour

Rosslare Europort is a seaport in County Wexford, Republic of Ireland. The harbour was first developed in 1906 to serve steam ferry traffic between Great Britain and Ireland. In addition to the 'landbridge' to Europe, where products are taken through Britain to reach the European continent, there has been growth in direct freight sailings to Europe from Rosslare since the UK's decision to leave the European Union.

The local population centre which serves Rosslare Harbour is also known as Ballygeary. According to the 2016 census, Ballygeary had a population of 1,200 people. For planning purposes, Wexford County Council also include nearby Kilrane Village, which had a population of 647¹⁵. In 2016, 21% of the population were aged 65 and over. This is significantly higher than the county average of 14.7%. It can be attributed to the popularity of the area as a retirement location. The population amongst the remaining age cohorts are below the county's averages.

Following the completion of the railway line from Wexford to Rosslare Harbour in 1882 and the agreement in 1894 to allow passengers to dock at the harbour, a new settlement developed to accommodate the many employees of the expanding port. Wexford County Council say that development has taken place in a somewhat uncoordinated manner so urban design opportunities have been missed in Rosslare Harbour, and the volume of HGV and car movements through the area can contribute to a poor sense of place. However, they go on to say that the area is well placed to maximise the benefits of tourism. The number of visitors who pass through the settlement going to/from the Europort offer significant opportunities to local businesses in the area, for example food, services, accommodation and in turn employment. There are also opportunities to expand cruise tourism at the Europort and maximise spin-offs for the local area, and the county.

¹⁰ [Holyhead \(Community, United Kingdom\) - Population Statistics, Charts, Map and Location \(citypopulation.de\)](https://citypopulation.de/en/uk/england/wales/anglesey/holyhead)

¹¹ [Profiling Places Wales](#)

¹² [Local Area Report for areas in England and Wales - Nomis \(nomisweb.co.uk\)](#)

¹³ [Profiling Places Wales](#)

¹⁴ [WIMD - Holyhead Town \(gov.wales\)](#)

¹⁵ [Volume 3 - Wexford County Development Plan 2022-2028.pdf \(wexfordcoco.ie\)](#)

The N25 road runs through Rosslare Harbour to Rosslare Europort, and runs north from the village to Wexford, where it continues westwards towards Kilkenny or drivers can travel northwards towards Dublin on the N11/M11. Three or four Irish Rail services run daily from Dublin to Rosslare Europort, along the Irish east coast. Buses run to Wexford from the port, for onward services.

2.5 Dublin Port

As the capital city of the Republic of Ireland, Dublin (Baile Átha Cliath in Gaelic) is an outlier in terms of population and size compared with the other port towns in the operation. The city has its origins in the ninth century. Dublin's metropolitan population is approximately 1.25m people. Failte Ireland¹⁶ says that the population of the Dublin Docklands area, which is the focus of the operation, is around 27,000 people, with 44,000 working there. It covers both sides of the River Liffey, roughly from the Talbot Memorial Bridge to the 3Arena entertainment complex.

Three hundred years ago, the only houses to be found in the docklands were in the small fishing hamlet of Ringsend. When opened in 1796, the Grand Canal Dock was the largest dock in the world and provided a gateway to the Grand Canal, connecting Dublin to the River Shannon. The dock at Dublin Port is the largest in the State, handling almost 50% of the country's trade. The area surrounding Dublin Port has seen substantial heritage attraction investment in recent years, including several Dublin Port Corporation projects, including the Diving Bell Museum and the Pumphouse Heritage Zone. Nearby, the EPIC museum traces Irish diaspora and emigration to other countries.

However, the Docklands Area has traditionally been characterised as being relatively disadvantaged with a higher than average percentage of its population being classified as coming from lower social groups than is the case for Dublin City & County as a whole. Earlier economic analysis of the area¹⁷ suggests an over-concentration among Docklands' residents who work in the area in Unskilled Manual grades, which they say reflects the general socio-demographic background and profile of the area.

2.6 Travel Information

2.6.1 Ferry Passenger Data

Ferry passengers are considered a key group of potential visitors to the five port towns because they are already physically close to two of the locations because of their travels. By highlighting the positive aspects of the locations, and the available tourism opportunities, the operation hopes that they will be able to convert this into footfall.

¹⁶ [DublinDocklands_Final-Narrative- 1.pdf \(failteireland.ie\)](#)

¹⁷ [Williams, J. & M. O'Connor \(2000\)- 'The Employment and Socio-Demographic Profile of the Dublin Docklands Area'.](#)

Proposals for doing so include exhibitions at the ports themselves and screenings of the documentary films by ferry companies on ships whilst passengers are on board. Is it recognized that many people have already made detailed plans for their journey prior to embarkation, but this may persuade passengers (in particular foot passengers) who have less formalized travel itineraries to visit the local area before moving on with their journey or offer a 'slow-burn' potential in which ferry passengers consider an extra period of time in either, or both, of the port towns as part of a future journey.

The number and profile of ferry journeys between the island of Ireland and the UK has changed significantly in recent years, because of Covid-19 and then the implementation of the UK's departure from the European Union. In 2019, the year before the pandemic, there were just over 1.7 million journeys between Dublin and Holyhead by ferry, around 870,000 passengers in both directions.¹⁸ Ferries from Rosslare travel to both Fishguard and Pembroke Dock. There were 221,000 journeys between Fishguard and Rosslare and 294,000 between Pembroke Dock and Rosslare. In total, around 260,000 passengers disembarked in Rosslare, with 111,000 disembarking in Fishguard and 144,000 in Pembroke Dock. Total figures for Republic of Ireland ports also include smaller numbers of passengers travelling on ferries from Cherbourg to Dublin and Rosslare, and from Liverpool to Dublin.

The Irish Maritime Development Office (IMDO) has published comparative figures for the years 2019-2021 for total Irish port usage.¹⁹ These show that the total number of passengers of Republic of Ireland ports in 2021 was only 38% of the figures in 2019. Rosslare was at around 42% of the passengers who travelled through the port in 2019, just above 240,000, and Dublin Port at 38%, about 670,000 passengers. The removal of Covid-19 travel restrictions in the summer of 2021 led to an increase in passengers compared to previous quarters. Based on the previous profiles, we can assume a similar reduction in passenger footfall for the Welsh ports.

Although the increase in late 2021 is welcomed, these figures contrast with the inter-UK passenger numbers for Northern Ireland to Scotland which have effectively returned to pre-pandemic passenger numbers in both Belfast and Larne. This is attributed to there being less restrictions on intra-UK travel since the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, driving a faster return to pre-pandemic passenger levels in Northern Ireland ports, when compared to Republic of Ireland ports. IMDO say that 'Once a phased reopening of travel and economic activity began across the United Kingdom, passenger numbers in Northern Ireland began to return swiftly.' They go on to warn that continued low passenger numbers expose the passenger ferry market to long term vulnerability and impacts the domestic market.

Figures from Tourism Ireland²⁰ for the year to date until April 2022, show ferry arrivals in Republic of Ireland ports 26% down on the same period in 2019.

¹⁸ [Maritime - CSO - Central Statistics Office](#)

¹⁹ [Irish Maritime Development Office \(2021\) Irish Maritime Transport Economist: Vol. 19, Dublin: Irish Maritime Development Office.](#)

²⁰ [PowerPoint Presentation \(tourismireland.com\)](#)

Noting the origins of the operation were already socio-economically deprived areas around the port towns, low passenger numbers remain a threat to the aims of the operation in increasing footfall and spend within local communities, as well as providing an existential threat to their viability. But they also represent an opportunity for the operation's outputs to be used to help drive passenger numbers through coordinated work between Destination Management Organisations (DMOs), local authority economic development teams, ferry operators and relevant national bodies.

3. Project delivery

Summary

- Covid-19 restrictions have curtailed the efforts to physically engage local communities across the five port towns and as such impacted the progress made across all the work packages. It has also directly impacted on ferry passenger numbers and as such visitor volumes connected to each port. The operation has also been influenced by the progress of Brexit negotiations and more recently the refugee crisis caused by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.
- Feedback from staff and contractors has highlighted satisfaction with the partnership working and governance arrangements for the operation. The Stakeholder Advisory Group was cited as providing valuable and timely guidance and support.
- Staff turnover had created challenges to maintaining delivery momentum and partnership working with the level of turnover associated with the use of fixed-term contracts, however the Programme Board have acted to recruit to posts to ensure that the contracted deliverables are achieved.
- Greater coordination with other cross-border initiatives should have taken place at an earlier stage to avoid any duplication of effort in the creation of tourism and business networks and to align marketing and communication activities.

This section of the report presents an overview of the delivery of the operation since launch. It outlines a range of external factors and design considerations that have influenced delivery of the constituent work packages and progress towards the stated longer-term goals.

3.1 Covid-19 impacts and external influences

The operation was launched in 2020 following a longer than anticipated period of design and development. It has not only been directly impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent restrictions imposed in Wales and Ireland, but also by the strict application of these restrictions in the academic institutions and local authority partners leading the delivery. In practice, these **restrictions have curtailed the efforts to physically engage local communities across the five port towns** and as such impacted the progress made across Work Packages 2, 3 and 5. It has also **directly impacted on ferry passenger numbers and as such visitor volumes** connected to each port. As a result, the true impact of the operation on tourism numbers and visitor dwell time is unlikely to be measurable at the cessation of delivery in July 2023.

Whilst the operation did pivot to online engagement approaches this has not enabled the same level of reach and participation that would have been possible through physical meetings. This is particularly true regarding efforts to engage local businesses and the ferry ports, one of the necessary steps to creating sustainable tourism networks.

Stakeholders also referenced **influences associated with the progress of Brexit negotiations**, with Irish ports benefiting from continued connections to the European Union whereas Welsh ports have experienced a period of readjustment and greater economic or investment uncertainty. It has been suggested that this has disproportionately impacted on business confidence in Welsh ports and as a result the level of business investment to realise the opportunities afforded by the increased focus on port heritage and profile delivered by Ports, Past and Present.

Finally, and more recently, the **refugee crisis caused by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict has served to limit some designated event hosting areas and accommodation offer within some of the ports**. Consequently, the combined capacity of the ports to host visitors (including day trippers and overnight stayers) has been constrained, the impact of which is likely to continue in the near future.

'Brexit has had a positive and negative impact. Wales & Ireland regional development programmes will cease at the end of PPP and the others. (There's) no real plan for how projects like this could be funded in the future. But Brexit has brought with it Levelling Up fund which some ports are applying to and benefitting from. There were lots of opportunities lost due to COVID and Brexit, but now new ones are emerging, so feels a sense of optimism with some 'green shoots' growing - people are trying to look to the positive, not dwell on the negative' **Project Team**

'Brexit has resulted in supplier issues from the UK, now with double VAT as it is outside the EU. Welsh ports (are) being impacted severely, where Rosslare is set to thrive, becoming the gateway to the EU port'. **Project Team**

'The ferry ports weren't very helpful in the main, but due to Covid they were fighting to survive so Ports, Past and Present (was) seen as a nice to have, not essential.' **Project Team**

These factors have been beyond the control of the Programme Board and Project Team and although mitigation actions have been taken, these factors should be taken into account when considering the following sections of this report. These factors have also meant that the creation of FTE jobs as not been possible within the timeframe of the operation.

3.2 Partnership working and governance

Work Package 1 of the operation has covered its project management and governance. The operational governance structure has ensured that regular reports on progress have been provided with oversight of the key deliverables and discussion on achievement towards deliverables and risks. **Feedback from staff and contractors has highlighted satisfaction with the partnership working and governance arrangements for the operation.**

Whilst much of the delivery was led 'in-house' by University College Cork (HEI), Aberystwyth University (HEI), the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies at the University of Wales Trinity St David (HEI) in Wales and Wexford County Council, work with contractors across the different work packages was reported as generally positive. **The Stakeholder Advisory Group was cited as providing valuable and timely guidance and support.**

'The project team has always been careful and strategic about meeting PPP objectives. The seamless move to online working at the beginning of the project has enabled the project to navigate the logistics of cross border working, and especially during a pandemic.' **Project Team**

'There has been a strong passionate team working on Ports Past and Present from the start which has benefitted delivery, they have regularly gone above and beyond, wanting to achieve more than just the minimum outputs.' **Project Team**

The main challenges associated with the delivery of the work packages related to high levels of staff turnover and the fact that **the project team were not embedded within the five port communities** which created difficulties in progressing partnership working (exacerbated by the pandemic and remote delivery). Staff turnover had created challenges to maintaining delivery momentum and partnership working with the level of turnover associated with the use of fixed-term contracts where staff have moved to take-up alternative employment towards the end of their contract period. This is a common challenge with funding programmes where staff are on fixed-term contracts rather than secondments. The Programme Board have acted to replace staff that have departed the operation to ensure that the contracted deliverables are achieved where possible.

Mixed views were fed back during stakeholder interviews regarding the extent to which the operation had collaborated with other cross-border initiatives such as Ancient Connections and Celtic Routes. Whilst some felt that the links and lines of communication across the three operations had been positive, supported by regular meetings, others felt that this had not sufficiently achieved tangible benefits such as co-ordinated delivery, aligned marketing and communications and avoiding duplication of effort (i.e. consultation fatigue for some stakeholders and communities).

Whilst the Project Team did attempt to coordinate with the other Ireland-Wales Interreg operations, including instigating a series of collaborative meetings facilitated by Planed, the ability to collaborate across operations was limited due to time and capacity constraints.

An important learning point for the design of future operations is the inclusion of actions that seek to identify and develop relations with operations with shared interests and goals. With hindsight, inclusion at the design stage of the various Ireland-Wales Interreg operations may have delivered operational efficiencies, avoided duplication of effort, and enabled pooling of resources where possible.

The absence of co-ordination specifically regarding the creation of tourism/business networks was specifically referenced as an area where greater planning and collaboration could have been taken place in the early stages of delivery.

The multi-faceted nature of the operation, involving a range of sectors and stakeholders, was commonly referenced as both ambitious and challenging. A small number of stakeholders felt that with hindsight the operation would have benefited from being more tightly focused and that **the Project Team should have included specific tourism expertise from the outset.** Whilst the value of the operation as a model of ‘collaborative research’ was highlighted at the final closure event in April 2023, this perhaps highlights a relative lack of focus on using the research and creative output to drive tourism growth.

'If planning a similar project, I would reduce the number of sectors the project was trying to work to. Balancing academic, heritage, business and tourism objectives has been difficult... business is about income and bed nights... heritage organisations can be more about volunteer time and experience, so the two compete.' **Project Team**

The main gap cited in the operation’s partnership working was the ferry operators who proved difficult to engage, in part due to the pandemic. This has remained a gap in the programme despite the considerable efforts of the Project Team to engage with the ferry operators, the implications of which are likely to directly influence its legacy and sustainability as outlined in the later section of this report. Similar challenges were highlighted in engaging Visit Wales and Tourism Ireland during and beyond the operation’s delivery (see later legacy section of this report).

3.3 Closing event

The [final closing event](#) of Ports, Past and Present project took place in University College Cork on the 25th, 26th and 27th April 2023 and was used to celebrate project outcomes including creative works, over 200 cultural heritage stories, and the new tourism business network.

The event was used as an opportunity to promote discussion and facilitate networking. Presentations and provocations were provided by a range of speakers with sessions on 'Regenerative Tourism: A new Mindset for a Flourishing Tourism Destination',²¹ 'Cultural Heritage Tourism as Sustainable Tourism'²² and 'The Port as Cultural Entrepôt'.²³ The event gave an international perspective on ports and was also used to discuss issues pertaining to the legacy of the operation (see later section of this report).

[The project team with some stakeholders at the launch of Kathy D'Arcy's *The Trip*, and of an exhibition about the project staged in The Hub, University College Cork, as part of the Closing Event]

²¹ Aisling Ward (Munster Technological University)

²² Colm Murray (PPP Stakeholder Board)

²³ Porscha Fermanis (University College Dublin)

4. Project achievements

This section of the report draws on internal monitoring data captured by the Project Team, responses to the stakeholder survey disseminated by Wavehill and feedback captured during one-to-one stakeholder interviews.

4.1 Creative connections

Summary

- The participatory approach to delivering the creative connections work packages has provided opportunities for local communities to engage in the creative process to build a sense of pride and ownership. The outputs from this work package have the potential to attract visitors, increase dwell time and improve visitor experience. However, without a clear destination marketing campaign the visibility of these may be low and they will not realise their potential.

The work delivered through the Creative connections strand of the operation (Work Package 2) focused on the administration of twelve commissions of £5,000 each to allow six writers and six artists to work with community groups on creative projects exploring the history and heritage of the five port towns and the journeys made across the Irish Sea.²⁴ Led by CAWCS in Wales and Wexford County Council in Ireland, the activity was delivered through the dissemination of a call-out for artists and writers across the five port communities and the commissioning of successful applicants.

The purpose of this work was to both deepen the knowledge and appreciation of the history and culture of the five port towns and crossings among local communities, which in turn would contribute to efforts to attract visitors to spend more time and money in the port areas through the creation of a structured set of experiences. This in turn would generate direct economic impacts for the port communities.

The approach of the commissioned artists has been participatory, providing opportunities for local communities to engage in the creative process to build a sense of pride and ownership. Multi-disciplinary artist and filmmaker [Zillah Bowes](#), for example, hosted a workshop with Fishguard Youth Centre which explored with the attendees some of the concepts relating to her photography work for the project.

²⁴ Commissioned artists included: Rua Barron and Hannah Power; David Begley; Zillah Bowes; Gillian Brownson; Kathy D’Arcy; Jon Gower; Robert Jakes; Julie Merriman; Peter Murphy; Augustine O’Donoghue; Marged Pendrell; and Peter Stevenson and Jacob Whittaker

The creative work arising from this work package has been launched and showcased across a range of events, including for example at the On Land's Edge Festival in Fishguard in September 2022 and at the Ucheldre Centre in Holyhead on in October 2022. In March 2023 a [Conversations with Artists](#) event hosted in Wexford County Hall provided an opportunity for several of the commissioned artists to talk about their work.

[Launch of the Creative Connections Exhibition at the Ucheldre Centre, Holyhead, on the 15 October 2022]

The work has been displayed and exhibited both locally and further afield and, in some cases, is being displayed permanently in the local area in venues including local libraries, heritage centres, port terminals or railway stations. Printed outputs (pamphlets and books, including children's stories, poetry, folk-tales and natural history) were given out free to communities, and audio and visual outputs (films, spoken word) have been made available to communities to re-use and re-purpose.

The work created through the creative connections work package has also been curated into a series of [30 'tours'](#) which are focused on stories and information that has the potential to attract visitors, increase dwell time and improve visitor experience. However **without a clear destination marketing campaign the visibility of these may be low and they will not realise their potential**. This highlights one of the considerations for the operation's legacy to ensure that the creative commissions and outputs can continue to contribute to visitor growth and experience beyond its closure.

The main learning point relating to this work package involves the level of budget attached to each commission. Feedback from some commissioned artists indicates that this was not sufficient to provide enough resource for artists to work meaningfully with communities in the creation of the artwork, with a danger that the activity was seen as tokenistic. Although other approaches could have been considered, including for example the use of an artist residency model in each of the port communities, this would have required considerably more resource to cover the five ports and was not as a result within scope of the operation.

It is important to note the impact of Covid-19 on the artist commissions, as the restrictions that ran through 2020 and 2021 meant that artists had to radically alter the plans for community engagement. Projects that were to be carried out in ports had to pivot online and this process was supported and facilitated by the St David team. Not all artworks are presented in the format first envisioned in the commission due to Covid, but what was produced was often more innovative as a result. As the work came to completion, several of the commissioned artists felt that they benefited from the support and the skill-set provided by the WP 2 team. This included the editorial and design skills in the production of the books and pamphlets produced for the port communities.

"I wrote it in supreme isolation so hadn't had much feedback, and since it's also the first piece I've written in a very long time it is so heartening to hear that it speaks to readers and listeners. I'm just delighted that it will be heard and I'm very thankful to you all for the gentle encouragement which enabled me to create it. I appreciate just how much work and time you've put into making this a reality and I'm just so grateful." **Commissioned artist**

Each of the artists are profiled on the Ports, Past & Present website and have featured in marketing and communications activity (work package 6). Some of the artists raised concerns that the operation was slow to provide payment and that they worked above and beyond their fixed fee for the work, with no flexibility in the operation's budget to provide additional payment. Although this is unfortunate, the commissions were agreed at the set fee from the outset. This rigidity was attributed to the approval process for any changes to the operation's finances through WEFO being inflexible despite the efforts of the Project Team.

The 12 creative commissions formed a key part of the Port Fest events, as is outlined below. Feedback about the Port Fests should be read in many cases as a response to these artworks as the creative works were exhibited, and many of the artists commissioned were asked to speak about their work at these events, for a speaker/facilitator fee. This to some extent mitigated the limited budget for the commissions. These events allowed the artists to meet each other in person, and some have gone on to work on further collaborations, as is the case with Robert Jakes and Peter Stevenson.

“I’m writing as one of the art practitioners who worked on the inspiring Ports Past and Present project to forge new creative connections and collaborations in and around the port towns. Through the project I met fellow artist, Robert Jakes who was working in Pembroke Dock, while I was in Fishguard. Robert and I realised we shared many ideas particularly about stories and folklore, so we then worked together as Creative Practitioners on an Arts Council Wales funded project in Gelliswick School in Milford Haven, opposite Pembroke Dock. This involved incorporating some of the skills we also brought to Ports, Past and Present. We introduced the children to their own local folk tales, helped them make a long-illustrated scroll about their local folk hero Skomar Oddy the Giant, and built a large carved crankie box and benches in the school grounds to leave them with a theatre space of their own to tell their stories. This was so successful that I will be going to New Zealand next year to repeat the project in a community garden in Kapiti. Sometimes, these projects make connections in unlikely but wonderful ways.” **Peter Stevenson, Commissioned artist**

[Robert Jakes 'Sea of Stories II', the original artwork, painted onto tile and displayed in the port terminal at Pembroke Dock, was so popular that an extension was commissioned by Waterford County Council to illustrate the journey between Dublin and Holyhead]

4.2 Documentary films

Summary

- Developing the content for the documentary films has enabled the operation to engage and involve a range of stakeholders, supported by extensive research by the academic teams at University College Cork and Aberystwyth University as well as the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies in Wales.

The third work package was focused on commissioning a series of short documentary films exploring the history and of stories of the five ports and their associated sea crossings. The process of **developing the content for these documentary films has enabled the operation to engage and involve a range of stakeholders, including representatives from heritage, nature and cultural organisations, community groups and local businesses.**

Along with the development of the content for the Port Places App, they have been **supported by extensive research by the academic teams** at University College Cork and Aberystwyth University as well as the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies in Wales.

The documentary films aimed to help publicise the ports and in doing so entice visitors to spend more time and money in the port towns. It was also hoped that the films would encourage port authorities to invest further in telling the story of the history and heritage of each port and their cross-border connections. The eight short documentary films and the feature-length documentary were launched between May and October 2022 and have to date achieved 15,153 combined views (Table 4.1 over page).

Table 4.1 Launch and views of the documentary films

Video title	Publication date	Views
Ports, Past and Present: Holyhead (2022)	Oct 24, 2022	5,198
Ports, Past and Present: Rosslare Harbour (2022)	Jun 24, 2022	3,527
Ports, Past and Present: Pembroke Dock (2022)	Aug 1, 2022	2,775
Ports, Past and Present: Fishguard (2022)	Sep 26, 2022	2,102
Ports, Past and Present: Dublin Port (2022)	Aug 17, 2022	1,551

Source: Ports, Past and Present monitoring data, May 2023.

The documentary films have been well received with feedback from stakeholders praising their quality and value in promoting the history and heritage of the five ports, bringing this to life through personal stories. The videos are hosted on [YouTube](#), and [Vimeo](#) providing a lasting resource for both tourism, education and heritage outcomes. More

importantly, all film and image files have been uploaded to the [Digital Repository of Ireland](#) to guarantee their free availability to any viewer and user at the point of access in perpetuity.

“The videos and stories produced have been of high quality”. **Stakeholder**

“The videos and material produced by the project could be showcased to the ports and ferry operators”. **Stakeholder**

The documentary films range from the relatively short videos of around 12 minutes in length of each port and the three ferry links between them to the longer [At the Water’s Edge: Stories of the Irish Sea](#) which is a feature length film of around 80 minutes in length. Shorter clips of around 2 minutes entitled [Port Voices](#) have been collated from the preparatory oral history interviews for the documentaries to enable viewers to delve into specific aspects of the life of those living in or with connections to the ports.

The intellectual property rights for the videos resides with the operation and its institutions but are required to be non-commercial in their use. This means that the videos can be reproduced and reused if they are attributed. This opens **the prospects of the documentary films anchoring any future destination marketing campaigns to raise the profile of the heritage of the ports and encourage growth in visitor numbers**. There is evidence that some of the partner organisations are already showing the videos in their buildings to raise the profile of the operation to staff, customers and/or visitors. This could be encouraged and replicated across all organisations represented on the Project Board to help extend the reach of the documentary films and encourage viewers to visit the ports in the future.

“I think it is making an impact. I work in Wexford County Hall ... the project has a display in the building, incorporating some of the films made by the project. I often see people stopping by and watching the video.” **Stakeholder**

The operation has not incorporated any destination marketing element and as such leveraging the use of the documentary films will require coordination and cooperation with relevant business and tourism bodies beyond the closure of Ports, Past and Present in July 2023.

As an additional avenue for promoting the film, the Aberystwyth University team published a free coffee table book with the title *Ports, Past and Present: Stories of the Irish Sea* (Eds. Rita Singer, Peter Merriman and Rhys Jones, 2023) with a print run of 1,050 copies. The coffee table book is an extension of the films while also promoting the Port Places app through the means of inserted QR codes that link to YouTube and the Google and Apple app stores. The book contains short histories of each port town and community, over 500 images from the documentary film and from unused raw footage together with interview extracts from each film participant. A short essay about the economic difficulties faced by each port community adds further critical context for the reader.

Designed and printed by Gomer Press from Llandysul, the book has been produced at a high quality with a sturdy, glossy hardcover and printed on quality paper. Copies were freely made available to the film makers, each participant, project stakeholders, small business owners, community and heritage groups. The Swiss Influencer Team from Come With Us 2 also raffled off copies to viewers of their videos during their round trip of the five port communities in March 2023.

[Come With Us 2 visiting Pembroke Dock]

In addition, copies have been deposited with the county libraries in Pembrokeshire, Ceredigion, Powys and Anglesey, as well as with the six copyright libraries in the UK. Owing to the limited print-run, free digital copies have been deposited with the [Digital Repository of Ireland](#), the [People's Collection Wales](#) and through [Aberystwyth University's research portal](#). The book has been in high demand and virtually all copies have been distributed by the end of June 2023.

‘On behalf of the Bardsey Island Trust I'd like to extend our thanks for the copies of the fantastic 'Ports, Past and Present - Stories of the Irish Sea' which you have given to the Bardsey Island Trust. We have placed a copy in each of the 10 houses we let as holiday lets and have given the remaining copies to the other permanent island residents including the fishers, farmers and Bird Observatory. As a tiny island in the Irish Sea this book work is of particular interest to us, our island residents and visitors.

Although to Enlli, the sea still plays a key role in day to day life, impacting fishing or visitor boats, we know that it would have played an even more significant role in the past. This book brings to life beautifully the richness of people and places connected to the sea through major ports. Although Enlli wouldn't have been a major port it would have still been a significant place for many in history when the sea was our easiest means of transport across long distances.

Many thanks once again for the copies and congratulations on an excellent project.’ **Cadeirydd, Ymddiriedolaeth Ynys Enlli / Chair, Bardsey Island Trust**

4.3 Bringing the past to life

Summary

- Port Fest Events have provided opportunities to showcase the work of the operation in covering and promoting tourism in the previously underappreciated ports. Opportunities to integrate and embed the work of the operation with other cultural festivals and events has also been realised.
- A total of 90 events and activities have been delivered by the operation, which has engaged at least 14,806 audience members and participants. Collectively they demonstrate the creative diversity of the operation and as a result wide appeal. They have been used to generate connections, explore collaboration opportunities, gather insight and data to inform creative and academic outputs and build momentum to raise the profile of the port stories.
- Those attending the events and activities agreed that their experiences had positively affected their sense of place and local identity and made them feel more connected to the other coastal port communities in the Irish Sea.

Two of the work packages (4 and 5) have specifically focused on bringing the past to life through a series of events and activities designed to uncover stories and hidden history within the five port communities. Sharing fascinating stories of ports in collaboration with the 5 port communities was key focus of the operation. This work was undertaken by WP 4 leads UCC, with contributions from members in all other organisations.

APRIL 2021
ROSSLARE PORT FEST 2021
20-22 April 2021

The team managed to publish 200 stories on the PPP website, 134 of which were written by crowdsourced contributors, many from the local port communities. The stories form a rich repository of port heritage to be mined for use in promoting ports as heritage tourism destinations. Many of these stories also directly addressed cross-cutting themes, such as environmental history and championing the stories of women. Examples include [‘Nest ferch Rhys – Princess of Deheubarth’](#), [‘My Family and Pembroke Dock’](#), and [‘North Bull Island’](#). These will form the content a new website called irishseastories.com, which will be linked to from the final project website. In addition to written stories, the WP 4 team also set up a podcast channel on [Anchor FM](#) (now Spotify for Podcasters). 11 podcasts on the site share the motivations of the site and touch on some cross cutting themes.

This has incorporated a series of community events, talks and performances. It has also covered the [Port Fest Events](#), which have incorporated online discussions about and the creative exploration of each of the ports past, present and future.

The development and planning of these events and activities has been underpinned by considerable research to enable the operation to engage, inspire and involve audiences. **Each Port Fest Event has provided an opportunity for the Project Team to showcase the work of the operation in covering and promoting tourism in the previously underappreciated ports.** The flagship events were hosted as follows:

- Rosslare Port Fest 20-22nd April 2021
- Holyhead Port Fest 18th May 2021
- Pembroke Dock Port Fest 11th June 2021
- Dublin Port Fest 22nd August 2022

Opportunities to integrate and embed the work of the operation with other cultural festivals and events has also been realised. For example, on September 25th, as part of the [On Land's Edge festival](#), Fishguard, Theatr Gwaun hosted Creative Connections (Work Package 2), an event showcasing some of the works created by writers and artists who have been working with communities across the 5 ferry port towns, and facilitated the Fishguard premiere of the 'At the Water's Edge' documentary film.

The operations' internal evaluation reports provide evidence of considerable work to engage a range of heritage and community groups across the five ports. This has been used to generate connections, explore collaboration opportunities, gather insight and data to inform creative and academic outputs and build momentum to raise the profile of the operation.

[Port Fest Dublin, August 2022]

The process of developing and maintaining links with such a wide array of partners has necessitated significant delivery capacity of the Project Team. Examples of organisations engaged are outlined in Table 4.2 below:²⁵

Table 4.2 Heritage and community groups engaged

Dublin	Fishguard	Holyhead	Pembroke Dock	Rosslare
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dublin Port Company • East Wall Heritage Group • St Andrew’s Resource Centre • Ringsend Irishtown Community Centre • Dublin Dock Workers Preservation Society • National Maritime Museum • EPIC Museum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • West Wales Arts Centre • Sea Trust Fishguard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Holyhead maritime museum • Anglesey Antiquarian Society • Ucheldre Centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commodore Trust • West Wales Maritime Heritage Society • Pembroke Dock Heritage Centre • Pembroke and Monkton Local History Society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rosslare Maritime Heritage group • Cois Barry House and Community Centre

Feedback from engaged organisations has been positive. The operation has helped to raise the profile of local heritage and community groups and in doing so, stories of relevance to understanding the history of development of the ports and port communities. The engagement of [Dublin Dock Workers Preservation Society](#), for example, showcased the stories of ‘three heroes’, namely Michael Donnelly, Patrick Currie and William Deans. Each played an important role in the port communities, advancing worker rights and improving the lives of those working within the ports.

Combined a total of 90 events and activities have been delivered by the operation, which has engaged at least 14,806 audience members and participants. Collectively they demonstrate the creative diversity, and as a result the wide appeal of the operation. Example events and activities include:

- Book launches (e.g. Jon Gower’s ‘A Flock of Words: Explorations of the Irish Sea’ and ‘The Turning Tide: A Biography of the Irish Sea’), Peter Stevenson’s ‘Fibbing from Fishguard’ (with live storytelling performances); Gillian Brownson’s ‘The Mermaid’s Purse’), [WP2 outputs]
- Live musical performances (e.g. Live performance of ‘We have always been your harbour’ by Wexford writer Peter Murphy and Musician Dan Comerford), in Dublin, Fishguard, Cork and Wexford), [WP2 outputs]
- Exhibitions of the output from the Creative Connections work package (2),

²⁵ Evidence gathered from internal evaluation reports provided by the Project Team.

- Film launches in each of the ferry port communities
- Biodiversity and heritage talks (e.g. Dublin Bay Biosphere, online),
- Guided walks (e.g. Stained glass in Pembroke Dock),
- Creative workshops (e.g. Sensational Seagulls), and
- Onsite talks (e.g. Rebels and Refugees: Irish Sea Crossings During the 1798 rebellion)

The operation has also hosted a regular series of online coffee mornings to support efforts to build a sense of shared community across the five ports. These events and activities have been well received with feedback captured by the Project Team, examples of which are provided below:

‘[I enjoyed] the rich history of the ports and it introduced me to some fantastic new artists. Lovely hour of my time turned into hours of intrigue’.

‘I think the film is essential viewing for anyone interested in the communities’.

‘I think the project and work is extremely successful and inspiring’.

‘Wonderful how this project has “recovered” the history not just of a big port like Dublin, but the small ports of the Irish/Welsh Sea as well and the interconnections of those ports’.

‘This was a brilliant film. It encapsulates everything that is so special about port and maritime history’.

‘Meeting people and sharing food with them, and watching a film that stresses what connects, not what divides us!’

The community spirit and activities on the film should promote more tourism and heritage/arts related events’.

Those attending the events and activities agreed that their experiences **had positively affected their sense of place and local identity and made them feel more connected to the other coastal port communities in the Irish Sea.** The events had also increased audience members’ awareness of the heritage of their local port.

4.4 The Port Places App

Summary

- The development and launch of the Port Places App forms one of the key deliverables for the operation and one that has perhaps the most significance for the operation's legacy. To date 444 users have downloaded the app, which suggests that further work is required if this tool is to realise its potential.
- The Project Team have identified an 'app champion' in each of the port towns to promote the app and encourage its use, and these are now in place in all 5 ports.

The development and launch of the [Port Places App](#) forms **one of the key deliverables for the operation and one that has perhaps the most significance for the operation's legacy**. The app was developed by University College Cork in partnership with the University of Lancaster's Safarnama app team. The operation supported and enhanced the development of the Safarnama Heritage App Platform in several significant ways.

Specific functionalities were devised in response to the operation's needs, in particular, the route design in the authoring tool and translation toggle. The collaboration allowed a number of broader developmental issues to be thought through more fully and to set the Heritage App Platform on a more solid footing. Three funding applications have benefitted from the developments, both in terms of software and ethos, undertaken during the University of Lancaster's collaboration with Ports, Past and Present, namely to the Arts & Humanities Research Council, Creative Communities Engagement Project and British Academy.

The collaboration has strengthened the App Platform in ways that will outlast the operation. New collaborative relationships were created and the relationships with community activists in the port towns will also continue with the Safarnama app team continuing to support and maintain the Port Places App and encourage and facilitate the authoring of new digital experiences.

The app is designed to enable visitors (and local communities) to explore the depth of history and heritage surrounding the five ports. Users that have downloaded the app can then download their choice of curated experiences, each providing a vision of port life, their heritage, history and creativity. The content and material for the app has been captured through the research and engagement work delivered by the Project Team and commissioned artists with local communities.

Promotional detail about the app has been made available on [YouTube](#) along with [guidance](#) for those wishing to create experiences (collections of locations and media) through the app. The intention is that the content of the app will be enhanced as more users download and create their own content.

The current content of the app showcases the detailed research required by the Project Team to bring the past to life, for example, exploring the legacy and commemoration of the 1797 Battle of Fishguard, which was the '[The Last Invasion](#)' of mainland Britain. App experiences currently range from an atmospheric Dublin theatrical tour, to a Pembroke Dock Town Trail, Rosslare Harbour tour and ferry crossing experiences, which is downloadable for when internet is not available on a ferry journey.

The app was launched on August 13th 2022 with a presentation and an app 'walk and talk' event. To 'bring the app to life' the team held an 'App Walk' in each port, a guided walk where participants were encouraged to look up content on the app. The walks were attended by c.100 participants across the 5 ports between October 2022 and May 2023.

[Pembroke Dock App Walk, led by Stakeholder Board Member Martin Cavaney. The walk was oversubscribed, with over 20 participants]

To date 444 users have downloaded the app, which suggests that further work is required if this tool is to support efforts to drive visitor numbers, increased dwell time and improved visitor experience and connection. During the process of developing and piloting the app, feedback has been captured from participants to gain a picture of the extent to which it contributes to increasing awareness of the heritage of the visited places, views on how the app may be used to support tourism and suggestions for improvements to its usability. Users fed back positively about the value of the app in changing their understanding of a place of region when they explore them.

‘It’s increased my knowledge about many buildings and features I walk past regularly in Dublin but have not previously known much about’.

‘Highlighted things I’ve never seen before and explained them’.

‘It helps to promote and explain the area to those who want the information’.

Users reported few suggestions on how to improve the app’s usability other than to incorporate links to other relevant sources of information or organisations. The consensus from users was that the app could support tourism and would help to enhance visitor experience, but it needed to be more clearly promoted and advertised by local Tourist Information Centres, travel operators and by Destination Management Organisations.

‘Tourist information centres need to promote this’.

‘It should be advertised on Failte Ireland and on flights into Dublin’.

‘Links from the tourism website and QR codes and info at the local offices, cafés, post office, etc; local publications: magazines, newspapers, etc’.

This is one of the key areas for consideration in terms of the operation’s legacy, namely, how to grow the profile and use of the app and build its content to provide a rich resource for visitors and communities across the five ports for years to come. Although the launch of the Port Places app has received positive coverage across a range of media outlets (e.g. local radio stations and news outlets). Without this continued focus there is a danger that the app will not realise its potential in contributing to the longer-term ambitions of the operation. The Project Team have identified an ‘app champion’ in each of the port towns to promote the app and encourage its use, and these are now in place in all 5 ports.

‘The heritage is of huge importance to us... the footfall off the ferry is vital to all the businesses in the town. It would be great if the day trips that arrive here could stay and explore the incredible heritage of Pembroke Dock instead of going to Pembroke Castle. I think the more knowledge our visitors have of the Ports Past and Present App, they are more likely to stay a while longer and explore further.’ **(Survey respondent)**

4.5 Tourism Network

Summary

- The creation of a self-sustaining tourism network was one of the key deliverables for the operation. Whilst attendances at some network events have so far been lower than hoped for, they do form part of a longer-term activity to connect and activate local businesses to support a process of raising the profile of the ports and attracting tourism.
- Feedback from some stakeholders has highlighted wider, external influences that impact on the ability of the ports to realise their potential and build on the momentum delivered by Ports, Past and Present. The most prominent was the current ferry timetables between Wales and Ireland but also the lack of accommodation offer and transport connectivity affecting the ports.

The creation of a self-sustaining tourism network was one of the key deliverables for the operation, established to link local authorities, tourism-related SMEs, community organisations and creative individuals on both sides of the Irish Sea to drive visitor numbers and grow the tourism economy. It is hoped that, after the operation's closure this network will continue to be fostered and advanced by key stakeholders and provide a forum for local businesses to share experiences of tourism in the port towns. It is expected that new employment opportunities may emerge as the potential growth areas for port-based heritage tourism become apparent.

As evidenced in the operation's internal evaluation reports, the Project Team has focused efforts on reaching out to local businesses from the early stages of delivery. The approach commenced with establishing a series of '[cross-coastal coffee mornings](#)' which included a heritage focus and aimed to foster an appreciation of the natural and cultural heritage within port communities. Local businesses were invited to these informal sessions, which commenced in February 2021 and included presentations from Project Team staff or a series of guest speakers (e.g. RMS Leinster Memorial Committee, Wexford wildlife ranger). Due to the restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic, many of these sessions were delivered virtually and may not have been as attractive or accessible to local businesses (who were themselves dealing with the implications of the pandemic).

In January 2022 the operation raised a tender opportunity for the creation of a tourism network, with objectives to build an online network of small tourism business owners and tourism professionals across the five port towns focused on promoting tourism business growth through heritage storytelling, the targeted use of social media, and links across the Irish Sea. Bofin Consultancy was appointed in July 2022 to form the new tourism business network for business owners and tourism supporting individuals in the port towns.

The first Tourism Network Event was hosted online in October 2022, aiming to promote the network and recruit members and then provide expert advice and guidance on how to build on the work of the operation to support businesses marketing and engagement plans. At the time of writing the network includes around 40 businesses and all members have signed an expression of interest to be part of the network.

[A collage of Irish Sea Ports Network members, photographs taken Feb-May 2023]

A series of Tourism Network Events have been delivered, including both training and networking, with the latter in particular facilitating discussion and exchanges of ideas on using the heritage of the ports and port communities to grow the visitor economy. Examples of events include:

- Heritage Through the Lens- 19th October 2022
- Develop Your Story- 23rd November 2022
- SMART Tools & Resources to Promote your Port and District- 11th January 2023
- Social Savvy Heritage Initiative- 15th February 2023
- Build Your Heritage Strategy- 15th March 2023
- Quality Collaboration for Seasonal Growth- 17th April 2023

Whilst attendances at some events have so far been lower than hoped for, they do form part of a longer-term activity to connect and activate local businesses to support a process of raising the profile of the ports and attracting tourism. This has been exacerbated by the challenge of engaging businesses remotely, with insufficient capacity and expertise to 'get boots on the ground' to bring the business community together.

Concurrently, since February 2023 the Project Team have engaged 64 business stakeholders as part of the process of developing the Tourism Business Network,²⁶ building groundwork to support the launch and envisaged continuation of the network as part of the operation's legacy. Since the launch of Ports, Past and Present the Project Team estimate that they have engaged over 250 business stakeholders.

'The network not only opened up a dialogue for us with other business owners but gave us an opportunity to listen & learn to the variety of ways the business could improve using different strategies. It opened up our minds to other ideas, strategies and the importance of moving with the times, especially being aware of the ever-changing audience/customer and what they are looking for in today's market. **(Business network participant)**

Due to the timing of the Network events, at least one participant noted that they had been unable to attend them and therefore could have benefitted from correspondence detailing and summarising the topics that had been covered through the workshops. In this sense, the reach of some events might have been limited by logistical factors and the lack of accompanying documents to accommodate the learning of those who could not attend.

'Unfortunately I wasn't able to attend the sessions due to timings and days. But having shared this with the coordinators I didn't receive any updates either on what was discussed or shared in the sessions. I think this would have been a useful element so I could utilise the training and skills to market' **(Business network participant)**

Although the operation had made some initial links with respective Chambers of Commerce or Port Authorities across some of the ports,²⁷ it has been challenging to develop these early conversations. This may, in part, be due to competition from the other cross-border operations of Ancient Connections, Celtic Routes and Portalis who each have tried to establish some form of tourism network over the same period. In the absence of a dedicated destination marketing campaign and resultant data on growth in visitor numbers, it has been difficult to retain business engagement given their focus on the 'bottom line' and need for a clear business case for being involved.

The operation has made efforts throughout to showcase port businesses and their role in port communities. This has been delivered through a combination of research and creative activities, most notably the [stories](#) gathered from businesses and local communities.

²⁶ Includes meetings completed between 8th February 2023 and 22nd May 2023.

²⁷ Includes Rosslare Chamber, Fishguard and Goodwick Chamber of Trade and Tourism, Wexford Chamber, Dublin Port Company and Rosslare Europort.

Examples include:

- [Sigginstown Castle, Rosslare](#)
- [The Green on Red Gallery, Spencer Dock, Dublin](#)
- [Red Onion Garden Café, Fishguard](#)
- [The Orient B&B, Holyhead](#)
- [The Shipwright Inn, Pembroke Dock](#)

Although the intellectual property for the range of creative products produced through the operation has potential to be used to support marketing and branding activities by businesses, there is a necessary step before this to address any gaps in technical skills or promote the value of heritage in driving visitor numbers, spend and footfall. In this regard, the operation is still within the very early stages of a longer journey.

Feedback from business owners and beneficiaries highlighted the value brought about by the Network in the form of opportunities to connect with other local businesses and gain exposure to different strategies for securing engagement. Through the Network events participants were enabled learn about the needs of a contemporary customer base and were introduced to the various ways in which peers had adapted their service to meet them.

Feedback from some stakeholders has also highlighted wider, external influences that impact on the ability of the ports to realise their potential and build on the momentum delivered by Ports, Past and Present. The most prominent was the current ferry timetables between Wales and Ireland and in particular their frequency, cost, arrival and departure times and future security. Several stakeholders indicated that the arrival and departure times were problematic as they often meant that passengers arrived into ports either too early or too late to encourage any dwell time and spend in the local economy. Anecdotally stakeholders also referenced a decline in foot passenger numbers who were perceived as more likely to spend time in the ports than vehicle passengers who would usually disembark and proceed through the port to their final destination.

The accommodation offer at the ports was also cited as problematic with some having either very limited or no room capacity and as such were not attractive for visitors to stay overnight. Whilst some stakeholders emphasised the considerable potential for empty or underutilised buildings to be repurposed into suitable accommodation options, any prospective investor would look for evidence of increased footfall and interest prior to deciding to invest. Initiatives such as the Irish Government's [Town Centre First policy](#) and the [Living City Initiative](#) (the Special Regeneration Area encompassing Dublin docklands) have potential to address these accommodation issues affecting the ports and port communities in any legacy phase of the operation.

The final external influence referenced by some stakeholders related to wider transport connectivity with suggestions that better infrastructure was needed to encourage visitors (either day trippers or overnight stays) using different modes of transport. The closure of train links to some of the ports and absence of regular bus routes was highlighted as particularly challenging.

Combined, these external influences are likely to continue to act as a brake on the ability of the Tourism Network to drive visitor numbers and grow the tourism economy. These factors are beyond the control of the operation and limit the operation's ability to support the port towns to become 'stopping places' and 'spending places' rather than just 'through places' for tourists, with an increase in tourism-related employment.

4.6 Communication and dissemination

Summary

- Between the 1st June 2020 and 4th May 2023 the website received visits from 37,667 users, over 53,025 sessions and involving 118,010 page views. The 8 documentary films produced have combined recorded 30,352 views, with an average of 316 views per film. Around one in seven of the documentary films produced have recorded over 500 views. The various social media channels have also worked to extend the reach of the operation.

Activity to communicate and disseminate the work and value proposition of Ports, Past and Present was delivered within Work Package 6, albeit in practice this work package was integrated into work packages 1 to 5.

At the outset of delivery a dedicated social media plan was created with the operation establishing a Twitter account and Facebook and Instagram pages. The internal evaluation reports chart the progress of this work package in building the profile of reach of the operation across these social media channels.

Lady Stanley neé Owen, a self-portrait. Source: National Library of Wales, c.1780. Public domain, out of copyright.

Audio Story: [The Curious Case of the Lady's Curse](#)

Gareth Huws sat down with Ports, Past and Present and shared the story of Margaret, Lady Stanley (neé Owen), the last heiress of the Owen family, an old local dynasty who by the mid-eighteenth century had lost much of their political influence and material wealth. Listen [here](#).

A dedicated, bilingual online newsletter was launched in March 2021 with monitoring around the total number of subscribers and new subscribers as well as open rates. In total 19 Newsletters have been produced and disseminated so far. These remain available through the [newsletter archive](#).

The newsletter provided a gateway for subscribers to access a wider range of resources, including audio stories, articles and

information about forthcoming events.

Source: November 2021 Newsletter

In terms of reach and performance, data has been provided for the reach of 26 monthly newsletters produced from March 2021 onwards. The total number of recipients combined for both English and Welsh language versions is on average 188 people with an open rate of around 51%. Whilst it is difficult to access benchmark data to determine whether this is a strong or weak newsletter reach, given the combined populations of the five port towns it is reasonable to suggest that the newsletter has not provided the strongest mechanism to raise awareness of the operation and its work.

However, the newsletter has not been the only tool for communication and dissemination. Between the 1st June 2020 and 4th May 2023 the website received visits from 37,667 users, over 53,025 sessions and involving 118,010 page views. The 8 documentary films produced have combined recorded 30,352 views, with an average of 316 views per film. Around one in seven of the documentary films produced have recorded over 500 views. The various social media channels have also worked to extend the reach of the operation, including:

- Facebook followers and interactions 821 followers and 3,370 post reach
- Twitter followers and interactions 1,575 followers and 77,700 impressions
- Instagram followers and interactions 335 followers, 2,288 accounts reached

What remains unclear is the level of support from relevant DMOs. Although the delivery of operation has engaged several DMOs²⁸ (national and local), there is no analytics to determine the extent to which this has boosted reach.

A dedicated destination marketing campaign, to help drive visitor numbers through the reuse and repurposing of the creative content and research produced through its delivery, did not form part of the original project plan. Had it done so, it could have run the risk of duplicating the work of the [Celtic Routes](#) operation, a joint project between Carmarthenshire and Ceredigion County Councils, Pembrokeshire Coast National Park in West Wales and Waterford, Wexford and Wicklow County Councils in South East Ireland, focused on boosting visitor numbers and spend in the less-explored areas that lie along the major transit routes between entry points and the well-known tourism ‘honeypots’ beyond.

Several stakeholders flagged this as a missed opportunity but also highlighted the absence of any national coordination of destination marketing that was needed to raise the profile of the cross-border links and connections between ports either side of the Irish Sea. Ports, Past and Present has used a combination of traditional media and digital media to promote its work and extend its reach. A press pack was created before each Port Fest event, to encourage print and radio coverage.

In February 2023 a communications company was contracted to provide support to showcase the final outputs of the operation and at the time of writing this work is ongoing, but coverage is forthcoming, such as articles in [The Irish Examiner](#), [The Echo](#) (Cork) and this piece in [The Irish Independent](#).

A small project was also commissioned in late April 2023 to resource two Swiss influencers to travel between all five ports providing Vlogs to publicise the towns and their heritage to their 100k followers and German tourist market.

²⁸ Visit Anglesey, Visit Pembrokeshire, Visit Wexford, Visit Dublin, Fáilte Ireland, Visit Wales & Tourism Ireland

'Visit Wales and Tourism Ireland appear to refuse to work together, they see a hard border with no cross publicity or promotion in port towns. Shame this hasn't altered, as very inward-looking approach'. **Project Team**

Feedback from stakeholders has highlighted concerns around a potentially crowded market, with other Interreg projects potentially targeting the same audiences within the port areas, as have wider heritage and economic development initiatives across Wales and Ireland.

4.7 Final outcomes and impacts

Summary

- The operation has engaged a wide range of stakeholders with influence and interests across local heritage and community-based regeneration.
- Approaching two thirds of stakeholders rated their town or port's heritage as either extremely or very important to their business or organization. This demonstrates that the operation has connected with a stakeholder group who realise the potential to draw on the heritage value of each of the ports and the cross-border story to deliver social and economic outcomes.
- Around four in ten stakeholders said that the amount of time tourists spent within their area had increased over the past year. It is not possible to accurately determine the extent to which the operation has influenced the number of, and time spent by tourists.
- Stakeholders report that Ports, Past and Present had raised the visibility of their local area's heritage in both the eyes of locals and tourists.
- Just over a fifth of stakeholders reported that they did not have enough information to determine any change in the importance of heritage within their local area. This highlights the potential role moving forward of the Tourism Network established by the operation as a forum to monitor and discuss the role of heritage in the local tourism offer.

The envisaged outcomes for the operation centred around coastal communities enjoying an increased awareness of their cultural heritage and new opportunities for heritage tourism. Our team administered a survey to ascertain levels of awareness of the port's heritage, the importance of this heritage in attracting visitors and views on whether the volume of tourists had increased over the last 12 months. The survey, administered at two points to provide a baseline and follow-up position, also captured feedback on different aspects of the Ports, Past and Present operation. Whilst these survey responses should not be regarded as definitive, they do provide a useful indicative view on the progress that the operation has made towards its intended outcomes and impacts, in particular given the absence of reliable data on visitor numbers, spend and dwell time across the five ports.

Responses were received from residents based within the five locations, the employees of organisations and businesses based within these areas, and employees of transnational organisations. In contrast with the baseline survey, which was completed by 53 responses, the follow-up survey data was made up of a sample of 69 responses. Despite this larger sample, there were not enough responses from each location for robust quantitative analysis based on place (Figure 4.1 over page).

The intention of this analysis is to consider the operation as a whole, rather than to provide detail on each of the situations in each port. Of the ‘other’ responses received, several were from the hinterland surrounding ports towns such as Holyhead and Rosslare, but not identifying as such. Additional base locations of those who responded to the survey included Cardiff, wider Yorkshire, and those in Ireland, which suggests that the reach of the project went well beyond the coastal communities targeted.

Figure 4.1: Where respondents’ businesses / organisations are based

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=69

Respondents were asked about the organisation that they represent, and which categories best describe their area of interest. They were allowed to tick multiple boxes. Just under a third of respondents (29%) identified themselves as part of a local history or education group, and were largely involved with museums, heritage & preservation societies across the port towns (Figure 4.2 over page). Other significant areas of work or interest included local tourism, accommodation, and the hospitality sector. **This demonstrates the progress of the operation in engaging a range of stakeholders with influence and interests across local heritage and community-based regeneration.**

Around a quarter (26%) of respondents reported themselves as an ‘individual’ with most of this sample not identifying with any specific organization or business. These findings are relatively in-line with those of the baseline survey, with the main difference being that the follow-up has had a higher proportion of respondents identifying themselves as ‘individuals’, unaffiliated with any group or organisation, which is likely to have been due to the delivery activity across the work packages over the last 12 months.

Figure 4.2: Which categories best describe your area of work or interest?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=66

Respondents were asked to consider how familiar they are with the town or port's heritage. The intention of this was to understand the knowledge base of participants responding to the survey. Like the baseline survey, respondents were generally found to have had a moderate to high degree of knowledge about their town or port's heritage (Figure 4.3 over page). Just over half of respondents (52%) were reported to have had either 'a lot' of knowledge within this field or were 'particularly knowledgeable' about this field. No respondents reported that they knew nothing about their town or port's heritage.

Such findings may reflect, however, the high proportion of respondents who have self-reported to be directly involved in, and beneficiaries of, the local heritage and tourism sectors. They therefore **may not be representative of the average local person's knowledge base or opinion towards heritage within their own town or port** as this would require a survey to be conducted among the wider community in each of the port towns.

Figure 4.3: How familiar or aware are you of your town or port's heritage?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=64

Respondents were asked how important the town or port's heritage is to their business or organisation, i.e., is it something that helps with marketing; drawing visitors and customers; contributes to your brand. Around a third of the sample (33%) gave the highest possible mark, that it was 'extremely important', with a further 27% saying that it was 'very important' (Figure 4.4 over page). In total, this represents 60% of participants in the survey. Many of the respondents within this sample were either employed within, or volunteers for museums, galleries and tourism organizations and boards.

'(Heritage) gives people a reason to stay longer in the town, rather than just go to the ferry port and not interact with the town. It also encourages people to do go on ferry day trips and explore the town for a few hours.' (Survey respondent)

“As a tourism network, the port is an entry point for visitors which makes it hugely significant to us. The history & heritage of the port is a tourist attraction in itself. Aspects of the area form part of our membership and there is potential for more local businesses to join in the future” (Survey respondent)

27% said that the town or port’s heritage was moderately important, whilst 5% said that it was ‘slightly important’. Such findings were largely in-line with those of the baseline survey. Whilst no respondents reported that they believed local heritage was ‘not at all important’, a further 11% said that this question was not relevant to them. None of the respondents gave an explanation as to why this was the case. This demonstrates that **the operation has connected with a stakeholder group who realise the potential to draw on the heritage value of each of the ports and the cross-border story to deliver social and economic outcomes.**

Figure 4.4: How important is the town or port’s heritage to your business or organisation?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=62

The survey asked a question about the extent to which, if at all, there had been change in the amount of time tourists spend in ports or towns over the past year, **around four in ten (39%) of respondents said that the amount of time tourists spent within their area had increased over this period** (Figure 4.5 over page). Out of this sample, 62% reported that the change was small, whilst the remainder (38%) reported that the change was substantial.

Figure 4.5: Have you seen a change in the amount of time tourists spend in your town in general over the last 12 months?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=33

In their explanations for their response, respondents commonly referred to factors caused by and related to the pandemic, such as the lifting of travel and social distancing restrictions and resultant increase in the numbers of tourists travelling domestically for holidays.

‘Like many UK tourist spots a mixture of staycations, the expense of going abroad, residual COVID related fears and that 2022 was a dry, sunny summer we experienced a substantial increase in tourism. Yet those reasons have now abated and bookings for 2023 are significantly lower than 2022, suggesting the reasons surrounding a boom in 2022 is no longer present.’
(Survey respondent)

Conversely a small proportion (6%) of respondents reported that the amount of time spent by tourists within their area had decreased within the same time period, with one respondent citing a lack of overnight accommodation as a contributing factor. Just over a fifth of the sample (21%) reported that there was no difference in the amount of time spent, with none in the sample submitting an explanation for the lack of change. A third of the sample (33%) felt they did not have enough knowledge to comment.

Given the limitations of the survey in terms of response rates and the absence of any measures of additionality, **it is not possible to accurately determine the extent to which the operation has influenced the number of and time spent by tourists.**

The survey also asked a question about the extent to which, if at all, there's been a change in the importance of heritage to the tourism offer in towns over the last 12 months (Figure 4.6 below). There was an equal proportion of respondents reporting either that the importance of heritage had increased in the last 12 months, or that there hadn't been any change in this respect, with each group individually making up 39% of the sample. Of the former group, the majority (69%) reported that the recent increase in the importance of local heritage had been 'small', with just under a quarter reporting that the change was instead 'substantial'.

In their explanations for their responses, respondents expressed that **Ports, Past and Present had raised the visibility of their local area's heritage in both the eyes of locals and tourists.** This may suggest that whilst such projects have contributed towards tourists' interest in the port towns and their history, they have also placed businesses and communities in a more informed position to meet and take advantage of this demand.

Figure 4.6: Has there been a change in the importance of heritage to the tourism offer in your town over the last 12 months?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=33

'The project has raised visibility about the heritage of the port, the town and the surrounding area.' (Survey respondent)

Some respondents, however, similarly acknowledged that as a relatively short-term project, the impact of Ports Past and Present on the importance of heritage across the port towns may be relatively limited, and implied that further plans to raise visibility should be implemented beyond its lifetime.

'Raising awareness is a slow process and is unlikely to happen overnight.' (Survey respondent)

Of the 39% who reported that there had not been any recent changes in the importance of heritage to their local tourism offer, none submitted any explanation for their stance. Just over a fifth of the overall sample (21%) also reported that they did not have enough information to determine any change in the importance of heritage within their local area. **This highlights the potential role moving forward of the Tourism Networks established by the operation as a forum to monitor and discuss the role of heritage in the local tourism offer.** No respondents reported that the importance of heritage to their local tourism offer had decreased in recent months. These findings therefore suggest that local and touristic perception of the importance of local heritage had at least been maintained throughout the final year of the project.

Respondents were further questioned on the extent to which they believed that a change in the perceived importance of heritage to local tourism offers was needed. Whilst the wording of the question enabled respondents to comment on the need for either an increase or decrease in the importance of local heritage, the comments submitted indicate that most respondents understood the question as referring to the former. Therefore, most submissions commented on the extent to which an increase of the importance of heritage to local tourism offers was needed (Figure 4.7 over page).

The survey found that **88% of respondents believed that a change in the importance of heritage to local tourism offers was needed either to a 'great' extent or to a 'significant' extent** (as indicated by the rankings of '4' and '5' on a 5-point scale). As highlighted previously, these rankings most likely refer to the need for an increase in the importance of heritage. Comments from respondents within these groups refer frequently to the importance of the heritage and tourism sectors within their local economies and the potential for growth within these sectors as contributing factors behind their rankings. **This provides evidence of support for a legacy arrangement for the activities and outputs produced by Ports, Past and Present to continue to champion the role of heritage as a driver for growth in the visitor economies of the five ports.**

'Tourism is a major revenue source for the area; anything that generates additional interest is most welcome. The collective marketing of the five towns as 'likeminded, linked communities' will really help drive pan-destination tourism, and perhaps more importantly, will foster a spirit of shared community and common values between the towns, and indeed the two nations. This is vitally important given the increasingly insular outlook of the UK since leaving the EU.' **(Survey respondent)**

'The heritage is of huge importance to us at the Dockside Art Gallery. The heart of the gallery's core focus is of Pembroke Dock Port / Dockside, with a passion for its history and community. The footfall off the ferry is vital to all the businesses in the town. It would be great if the day trips that arrive here could stay and explore the incredible heritage of Pembroke Dock instead of going to Pembroke Castle.' **(Survey respondent)**

Figure 4.7 To what extent do you believe that a change in the perceived importance of heritage to local tourism is needed

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=33

Comments such as those provided above indicate that the connections between heritage, tourism and localised economies are well-known and established amongst those that responded to the survey. Similarly, other comments have indicated **a perception that the heritage features of port towns are underutilised and hold untapped potential to attract visitors, increase visibility and help counter negative perceptions of the towns.**

‘In themselves port towns are not generally places which attract visitors, as a destination per se. Yet they have much to offer in terms of historical interest. The project aimed to address that weakness, adding in the case of Fishguard, a greater variety to the product mix of North Pembrokeshire.’ **(Survey respondent)**

A couple of respondents conversely commented that either heritage did not factor in as significant visitor attraction in their port town, or that recent efforts to bring visibility to local heritage were unlikely to have a long-term impact on tourism.

‘There have been projects to try and bring more awareness of the heritage of the town, however as far as I am aware these have been short term and will not necessarily bring in or make new tourists aware of the heritage.’ **(Survey respondent)**

Respondents were asked about the degree of information they heard or seen about the operation. Just over a half of respondents (54%) reported that they had either seen or heard 'a great deal' or 'a lot' of information about the project (Figure 4.8 below) with 30% reporting that they had seen or heard a 'moderate' amount and around one in seven (14%) a 'little' amount and 2% reporting that they had seen no information about the project.

These results differ somewhat with the baseline results, with the main differences being that the follow-up data shows a higher proportion of respondents reporting that they had seen a 'great deal, and a smaller proportion of respondents reporting with 'a little'. Such a finding is expected, however, given that the follow-up survey was distributed following the project's outputs and, therefore, at a time when the project had greater visibility across the port towns.

Figure 4.8: The degree of information respondents had seen / heard about the project

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=56

Respondents were asked to what extent they were aware of a range of work package outputs already delivered by the project. This included not being aware of an output, being aware of an output but not having participated or used it or being aware of an output and having used it.

As had similarly been found in the baseline survey, the greatest awareness and use was of the online heritage stories relating to the port towns. Just over half of respondents (52%) (Figure 4.9 over page) said that they were aware of, and had participated, in this aspect of the work, as opposed to 33% who said that they were aware of, but had not participated in this strand, and 15% who were not aware of this strand.

Again, as found in the baseline, the output area with the least awareness was the Port Places app for tourists and communities with 39% reporting that they were not aware of this output, with just over a fifth of the sample (22%) having used it. 39% said that they were aware of the app, but not used it.

Figure 4.9: To what extent are you aware of the following PPP outputs and have used or taken part in these?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=55

This shows **an opportunity to better promote the app**, which had been soft launched approximately a year before the writing of this report. It is anticipated that the ‘app champions’ who are set to be based in each port town will contribute towards a rise in the visibility and usage of the app amongst both locals and tourists.

Community engagement in creative commissions was the output which had more awareness, but less engagement. This is perhaps explained as being a more closed participation, compared with others which have more opportunities to participate. Just over a quarter (28%) had taken part in this whilst just under a half (46%) were aware of this strand. 26% said that they were not aware of the strand.

These findings are relatively in-line with the findings from the baseline study, with the main difference being that the proportion of respondents who were not aware of each event is comparatively smaller. It would also appear that the various levels of awareness and participation are correlated with engagement in the programme, and those furthest from the operation who completed the survey have a lower awareness whilst those more central to the activities have a greater awareness and participation. Again, it should be remembered that this is not a random sample completing this survey but chosen by operational staff and those already signed up to receive newsletter or following via social media.

Whilst respondents were asked the extent of which they were aware of the outputs which had already been delivered by the project, in the same vein they were also asked for their input on the seven outputs currently being developed and delivered at the time of this report. As this consists of the first time those involved with the operation have been asked to share their thoughts on these outputs, there cannot be comparison with a baseline.

The greatest awareness and use were of non-fiction 'Port Films' relating to the heritage behind the port towns. Just over two thirds of respondents (63%) (Figure 4.10 over page) said that they were aware of, and had participated, in this aspect of the work, as opposed to a quarter (25%) who said that they were aware of, but had not participated in this strand, and 13% who were not aware of this strand.

The output package with the least awareness had been the signage which was displayed in port centres to promote the online 'Port Stories' and the 'Port Places' app. 45% reported that they were not aware of this output, with just over a fifth of the sample (22%) having used it. 45% said that they were aware of the app but had not used it. This may be partially explained by the fact that apart from [Rob Jake's 'Sea of Stories'](#) in the terminal at Pembroke Dock, no signage is currently in place, although this is still a live part of the operation.

The workshops aimed at helping professionals and businesses with social media marketing was the output which had more awareness, but less engagement. This is perhaps explained as being a more closed participation for tourism-related bodies, compared with others which have more opportunities to participate. Just over a fifth (22%) had taken part in this whilst a half (50%) were aware of this strand. 28% said that they were not aware of the strand.

Figure 4.10: To what extent are you aware of the following PPP outputs and have used or taken part in these?

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=32

The previous question asked respondents whether they had participated in any of the 7 identified outputs from the operation and rate their participation experience based on their level of usefulness to them and their organisation. This was limited to the outputs which they had indicated they had used. Respondents gave their answers on a 5-point Likert scale which ranges from 'not useful at all' to 'extremely useful'. There was a further opportunity for respondents to indicate that they had not participated in them.

There was greatest satisfaction with the output relating to the community engagement in the project documentary films, whereby all respondents who had engaged with the output either deemed it 'extremely useful' or 'very useful'. Respondents were also highly satisfied with the online heritage stories, where 85% found the output either 'extremely' or 'very' useful (Figure 4.11 over page). It is interesting to note that the highest levels of satisfaction were found with the outputs that allowed the greatest opportunity for in-person relationship building, for example through community engagement and co-creation. This suggests that the operation would likely have achieved stronger impacts had the pandemic not limited the face-to-face engagement and onsite work for much of the delivery period.

There was the least satisfaction with the outputs relating to the monthly online coffee mornings and the community engagement in creative commissions work, with just over a fifth of the former sample (21%) reporting that the output was either 'not useful at all' or 'slightly useful', and 17% of the latter sample reporting that the output was 'slightly useful'. This still means, however, that the majority of respondents within these two samples reported that the outputs were at least reasonably useful.

The numbers were roughly constant across the six outputs, although there were slightly fewer at the higher end who were satisfied with the Port Places app, with just under three quarters (72%) who found it at least 'very useful'.

Figure 4.11: Extent to which respondents found the outputs useful

Source: Follow-up survey data, N=32

Respondents were again asked the same question regarding the seven outputs currently being delivered by the project (Figure 4.12 over page). There was greatest satisfaction with outputs relating to the films produced, including both their in-person screenings and those that can be accessed online. 84% of respondents found the non-fiction 'Port Stories' films to be either 'extremely' or 'very' useful, whilst 80% also found the in-person screenings at of fiction films at port terminals and local communities to be either 'extremely' or 'very' useful.

There had been the least satisfaction with outputs related to the Tourism network and its social media workshops, with a quarter (25%) of respondents reporting that the former output had been either 'not useful at all' or 'slightly useful', and 14% of respondents reporting that the latter output had been 'not useful at all'. This still means, however, that the majority of respondents within these two samples reported that the outputs were at least reasonably useful. Again, the response rate for this question was significantly lower than that of other questions, with 12 respondents informing the follow-up data. This may have resulted in skewed or less representative results.

It is worth noting that this element of the project was the last to be implemented on the 'ground' (late 2022 and virtually). Its output and success are contingent on relationship building among people only getting to know one another online and to engage with concepts of collaborative working around place-based tourism and destination marketing. The first opportunity for stakeholders to enjoy a face-to-face meeting was at the closing event in April 2023. As such, sustaining the momentum through the project's legacy will be vital to realising the emergent potential of this fledgling network.

With the caveat that the stakeholders responding to the survey were individuals and organisations with a connection to and interest in local heritage and/or involved in different aspects of the operation, responses are positive. Delivery of Ports, Past and Present and helped to bring groups together, raise visibility and awareness of the respective town's heritage and highlighted its ongoing potential to deliver positive social and economic outcomes. This demonstrates strong momentum to support any legacy activity across the five ports beyond the close of the current operation.

Figure 4.12: Extent to which respondents deemed each output useful

■ Not useful at all ■ Slightly useful ■ Reasonably useful ■ Very useful ■ Extremely useful

Source: Follow-up survey data. N=12

4.8 Cross-cutting themes

Summary

- Ports, Past & Present has undertaken a range of activities to ensure compliance with the Sustainable Development CCT including sustainable transport initiatives, the use of green procurement processes and incorporation of environmental issues and themes within creative commissions.
- Delivery of the operation has contributed towards efforts to tackle poverty and social exclusion, in particular by ensuring reach of community engagement activities to disadvantaged or underrepresented groups. It has also helped to build capacity and skills both within port communities and working collaboratively with schools and youth groups.
- The operation has taken forward a range of actions to ensure compliance with the equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming strategic aims, overseen by an Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming Champion.
- Combined, the operation has provided a positive contribution to several goals for The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015.

ERDF programmes funded under Priority Axis 3 require evidence of actions taken to address a range of cross-cutting themes (CCTs).²⁹ The Ports, Past & Present operation has reported on the following themes: (1) Sustainable Development, (2) Tackling Poverty and Social Exclusion, (3) Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming, and (4) Welsh Language. CCT indicators and targets have been set to support the delivery of the programme CCT objectives. Projects supported by the Structural Funds are required to contribute to achieving these targets.

4.8.1 Sustainable Development

The evaluation assesses actions taken to address the CCT of Sustainable Development by analysing project monitoring data and corroborating evidence in stakeholder interviews. Partners illustrated examples of where they have undertaken relevant activity that relate directly to Sustainable Development and also to the wider Wellbeing of Future Generation priorities. The key ESF programme objectives to achieving sustainable development are to:

- Promote environmental awareness and good practice in the implementation of activity;
- Integrate sustainable development into operations undertaking awareness raising education and training programmes;
- Support participating employers to adopt or improve Sustainable Development strategies;
- Promote social justice and equality of opportunity; and
- Recognise and promote health and wellbeing as one of the corner stones of a healthy, vibrant economy.

²⁹ WEFO (2018)- 'Cross Cutting Themes Key Document – European Social Fund. Integrating the Cross Cutting Themes across the 2014-2020 European Structural Funds'.

The key indicators of sustainable development that the operation was expected to contribute to include:

- Develop an organisational Eco Code
- Local sustainable supply chain development
- Integration of small-scale Green infrastructure
- Integration of small-scale Blue infrastructure
- Activity which is supporting bio-diversity on a site funded through SF's
- Development of an organisational Travel Plan and sustainable transport initiatives
- Resource efficiency measures
- Site environmental management plans
- BREEAM excellent where applicable
- BREEAM very good where applicable
- Attainment of CEQUAL for construction activity
- Use of Sustainable Urban drainage Systems (SUDS) where applicable

The examples below illustrate how Ports, Past & Present has undertaken activities to ensure compliance with the Sustainable Development CCT as a minimum:

- A project Eco-code was created during the mobilisation phase which provided tips for maintaining the cross-cutting theme of environmental sustainability. This was shared with project partners and displayed at partner sites. Environmental efforts have been shared on the project's social media channels through the recurring 'eco-tip of the day'.
- The project established a champion for sustainability to ensure that environmental sustainability was integrated into project practice. Examples of successful integration of sustainability has included:
 - The use of virtual meetings
 - Use of sustainable transport initiatives including car-pooling by staff to minimise vehicle emissions and for cross-border travel using ferry routes rather than flying
 - Resource efficiency measures including switching off devices when not in use and minimising paper use
 - The use of Ireland's [Green Public Procurement](#) (GPP) guidelines to govern all procurement associated with the operation
 - Promotion of natural heritage to support efforts to raise awareness of sustainable travel and green tourism
 - Incorporation of environmental issues and themes within creative commissions
 - Exploring plans for Eco-tourism within the activities of the established tourism network

The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015 Act puts in place a 'sustainable development principle. Which tells organisations how to go about meeting their duty under the act. The Act is also closely linked with the Environment Bill and the Planning (Wales) Bill, which together place an emphasis on the need for area-based evidence and a focus on long term planning.

In our view, the delivery of Ports, Past and Present, as outlined above and using its dedicated Eco-Code and exploring eco-tourism, has been aligned with the sustainable development principle. It has contributed specifically to 'Resilient Wales' one of seven key well-being goals in the 2015 Act, which outlines a goal to create a nation which maintains and enhances a biodiverse natural environment with healthy functioning ecosystems that support social, economic and ecological resilience and the capacity to adapt to change. It has also contributed to the 'A prosperous Wales' goal by acting on climate change and the efficient and proportionate use of resources.

4.8.2 Tackling Poverty and Social Exclusion

Tackling poverty and social exclusion is a European Commission and Welsh Government commitment which will focus on actions to create employment and progression opportunities and will help people to access those opportunities. The programme also aims to increase the mobility of those that are unemployed, work ready or underemployed. Longer term benefits can also be realised from sustainable employment including enhanced well-being. The key Tackling Poverty CCT objectives for the ESF programmes in Wales are:

- The creation of jobs and growth providing employment opportunities for those who are out of work;
- Tackling barriers to employment such as poor skills, lack of childcare or limited transport options, helping more people to access employment opportunities; and
- Focussing on growth, aligned with skills development interventions, enabling those experiencing in-work poverty to access more highly- skilled, better paid jobs.

The key indicators for tackling poverty and social exclusion that the operation was expected to contribute to includes:

- Activity which builds skills within the community
- Mentoring / advocacy activity
- Peer support activity
- Volunteering schemes
- Organisations paying the living wage

The examples over page illustrate how Ports, Past & Present has undertaken activities to ensure compliance with the Tackling Poverty and Social Exclusion CCT as a minimum.

- Community engagement activities ensuring that community members from disadvantaged backgrounds or minority groups are reached and that all events and activities are fully accessible. This has included making links with established Gypsy, Roma and Traveller organisations and refugee groups. Efforts were also made to hosts events, activities and creative outputs in local libraries and community centres to reach groups underrepresented within the traditional heritage visitor profile.
- Building capacity and skills within communities through research activities and events (e.g. coffee mornings and knit and natter groups) and the tourism network as well as making links to key anchor organisations within communities (e.g. community centres and social enterprises)
- Working directly with schools and youth groups as part of creative activities
- All community-based events were free to ensure that cost was not a barrier to participation.

The activities undertaken by Ports, Past and Present have in our view directly contributed to ‘A more equal Wales’ goal of The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015 Act, which articulates a desire to create a society that enables people to fulfil their potential no matter what their background or circumstances, including their socio-economic background and circumstances. It has also contributed to ‘A Wales of cohesive communities’ goal through its commitment to including and engaging local communities.

4.8.3 Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming

The integration of equal opportunities, gender mainstreaming and the Welsh language (which we also include in the Equal Opportunities CCT) is important not only for legal reasons, but also because overcoming inequalities between different social and demographic sections of society contributes to the overall effectiveness of the activity delivered by the programmes. The key indicators for equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming that the operation was expected to contribute to includes:

- Positive action measures supporting women
- Positive action measures supporting BME people
- Positive action measures supporting young people
- Positive action measures supporting older workers
- Positive action measures supporting disabled people
- Positive action measures supporting other
- Activities which challenge occupational segregation
- Equal Pay activity
- Activity supporting female participation in STEM
- Disability Access Group engagement
- Workplace health programmes supported
- Childcare provision
- Other care provision

The examples below illustrate how Ports, Past & Present has undertaken activities to ensure compliance with the equal opportunities and gender mainstreaming strategic aims as a minimum:

- Establishing an Equal Opportunities and Gender Mainstreaming Champion to oversee compliance across all aspects of delivery
- Achieving a gender balanced staff team and artist team and ensuring the use of inclusive recruitment practices to ensure that job opportunities have been made available to all individuals, including those with protected characteristics in line with the UK Equality Act 2010 and the Irish Employment Equality Acts 1998–2015.
- Monitoring the gender balance of speakers and contributors at events to encourage greater female representation.
- Partner universities participation in the [Athena SWAN](#) programme which is an equality charter mark framework and accreditation scheme established and managed by the UK Equality Challenge Unit in 2005 that recognises and celebrates good practices in higher education and research institutions towards the advancement of gender equality: representation, progression and success.
- Ensuring balanced representation of women in the heritage stories and material produced by the operation.
- Ensuring that all social media posts and communication output is accessible for those with visual impairment and support those using assistive technology.
- Ensuring that all project offices are fully accessible for those with mobility issues
- Undertaking positive action to support people to engage with virtual events and activities and ensure digital accessibility

The activities undertaken by Ports, Past and Present have in our view directly contributed to ‘A more equal Wales’ goal of The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015 Act, which articulates a desire to create a society that enables people to fulfil their potential no matter what their background or circumstances.

Welsh Language

The Welsh Government wants Wales to be a truly bilingual nation where people can choose to live their lives through the medium of either Welsh or English or both and where the presence of the two languages is a visible and audible source of pride and strength to everyone. In order to fulfil that vision, the Welsh Government has made a commitment in ‘Cymraeg 2050 – A million Welsh speakers’, the National Action Plan for a Bilingual Wales and its Welsh Language Scheme to mainstream the Welsh Language across policy areas. European Structural Funds can play an important role to support efforts to grow the Welsh language within the context of economic growth and job creation.

Operations can contribute to these aims by:

1. ensuring that all operations and grant-funded services are available through the medium of Welsh and that these services are actively promoted;
2. ensuring that all operations contribute to positive outcomes for the Welsh language, such as:
 - a. increased use of Welsh by participants;
 - b. increased provision and use of Welsh language services;
 - c. improved Welsh language skills;
 - d. enhanced economic opportunities in Welsh-speaking areas;
 - e. increased awareness of the benefits of the Welsh language for future employment opportunities and economic development.
3. monitoring progress and positive outcomes regarding the Welsh language.

In addition to contributing to the Welsh Government's strategic aims for the Welsh language, implementing the above measures would contribute towards compliance with the requirements of the Welsh Government's Welsh Language Scheme and, in due course, Welsh Language Standards under the Welsh Language (Wales) Measure 2011. The key indicators for Welsh language that the operation was expected to contribute to includes:

- Activity promoting the Welsh language
- Activity supporting speakers of the Welsh language.

The examples below illustrate how Ports, Past & Present has undertaken activities to ensure compliance with the Welsh Language strategic aims as a minimum.

- Establishing a Communications Plan and incorporating Welsh language within project material, including the operation's website, social media posts, publicity, newsletters and output material and the Port Places App
- Nominating a Welsh language champion
- Ensuring that Welsh language was built into the technical architecture of the operation's heritage platform Omeka
- Promoting and including Welsh language in the commissioned films
- Ensuring that Welsh partners engage wherever appropriate with the operation's Welsh first language stakeholders in their chosen language

The main issue experienced by the operation in relation to this CCT was the capacity to pay for translation for all outputs. The delivery of Ports, Past and Present has in our view provide a strong contribution to actively promoting the Welsh Language and supporting speakers of the Welsh Language. In doing so, it has adhered to the requirements of the Welsh Language Standard and The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015 Act goal of delivering 'A Wales of vibrant culture and thriving Welsh language'.

5. Legacy and sustainability

Summary

- There is a strong desire from stakeholders for the operation to establish a legacy vehicle to build on or sustain the momentum achieved through its delivery to date.
- Realising the potential for the history, heritage and connections between the five ports to contribute to future growth in visitor numbers and the tourism economy requires many of the outputs of the operation to be taken-up, viewed, reused and repurposed.
- There is a danger that without coordination there will be unnecessary duplication of effort across the Interreg cross-border projects and opportunities for alignment will be missed
- The future funding position is unclear given each nation will now proceed with different funding regimes. However, in principle, the aspirations and objectives of the operation continue to align with those of both Interreg and UKSPF
- The Ireland-Wales shared statement and joint action plan for 2021 to 2025 sets out 6 areas of cooperation, which includes Trade and Tourism and Culture, Language and Heritage and a commitment to initiate exploratory discussions to foster potential cooperation and collaboration between their respective tourism agencies. This has direct relevance for the legacy of Ports, Past and Present.

What is evident from the internal evaluation reports, analysis of the outputs from the respective work packages and responses to the survey of stakeholders is the strong desire for the operation to establish a legacy vehicle to build on or sustain the momentum achieved through the operation and deliver a stronger economic impact for the ports. Whilst steps have been taken by the Project Team to develop a project legacy plan, including discussions at the Stakeholder Advisory Board Event held in March 2023, the implementation of this plan will be guided by the level of capacity and resource that can be secured. This is, at the time of writing, currently uncertain.

Realising the potential for the history, heritage, and connections between the five ports to contribute to future growth in visitor numbers and the tourism economy requires many of the outputs of the operation to be taken-up, viewed, reused, and repurposed by organisations and communities with an interest in and connection with the five ports. Although many of the creative outputs, documentary films, heritage stories and other publications will be retained within the [Digital Repository of Ireland](#)³⁰ and [People's Collection Wales](#)³¹, this is unlikely to be achieved without some coordinating capacity.

³⁰ Digital Repository of Ireland is a research performing organisation and national Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) for Ireland's humanities, cultural heritage, and social sciences data.

³¹ People's Collection Wales is a free website dedicated to bringing together Wales's heritage.

Those involved in the delivery of the operation feel confident that Ports, Past and Present can continue to deliver positive impacts with regards to cross-border connections beyond its closure, but that greater collaboration was required between tourism bodies across the ports as well as supportive policies to enable and encourage cross-border delivery.

'The ideal legacy would be for Ports, Past and Present to have its own legs to continue on its own following the end of the funding, and that the communities will continue to talk and work together, and that the ports will still have a connection... in reality, some of the processes will continue, but won't without someone there to co-ordinate them... one positive legacy will be the online project archive available and the public website and app.... although continuing to raise awareness of the fact they exist will be difficult with no Project staff'.

Project Team

'Ultimately, Ports, Past and Present will have benefitted port town communities, but a lot of the benefit is currently intangible... the true benefit will become apparent over the next 2 to 3 years'. **Project Team**

One of the complicating factors for thinking about the operations' legacy is the need to consider that other Interreg cross-border projects will be exploring their own legacy covering a similar period. There is a danger that without coordination there will be unnecessary duplication of effort and opportunities for alignment will be missed. In this regard, the Project Team have been involved in discussions with other schemes also due to close over the next few months to consider a broader legacy vehicle for cross-border heritage and tourism activity moving forward.

One of the frustrations raised during consultations was the perceived lack of joint working between Failte Ireland, Tourism Ireland and Tourism Wales and sub-national DMOs, which created uncertainty around who would take on responsibility for coordinating and managing the operations' legacy and ensuring that the outputs have a longer-term life and use. Strategic discussions were also required to address more structural issues affecting the ports and their potential to realise the benefits of heritage driven tourism such as the frequency and timetabling of the ferry routes, transport connectivity and place marketing.

Furthermore, feedback captured by the Project Team since the launch of the operation highlights that many of the port communities report a long-standing dearth of engagement from the port and ferry sectors, despite their dependence on the labour and services provided by those same communities. This points to a broader political issue and a need for maritime development bodies and transport ministries in both jurisdictions to work with those sectors to develop and coordinate ring-fenced community development initiatives in and around the Irish Sea ports.

The future funding position is also unclear given each nation will now proceed with different funding regimes, with Ireland remaining within the EU's Interreg scheme up to 2027 and Wales securing investment through the UK Shared Prosperity Fund. Limited clarity on prospects for future cross border collaboration between Wales and Ireland was forthcoming in the Welsh Parliament Finance Committee's recent report on Post-EU funding arrangements.³² The ability to coordinate and align these respective funding streams to support a cross-border initiative has yet to be tested. However, in principle, **the aspirations and objectives of the operation continue to align with those of both Interreg and UKSPF.** The UK Government, working with the Welsh Government and the Welsh Local Government Association, has established an interventions list for each of the three investment priorities of the UKSPF.³³ This includes:

Communities and places

- W4: Enhanced support for existing cultural, historic and heritage institutions that make up the local cultural and heritage offer.
- W6: Support for local arts, cultural, heritage and creative activities.
- W8: Funding for the development and promotion of wider campaigns and year-round experiences which encourage people to visit and explore the local area.

Supporting local business

- W17: Funding for the development and promotion (both trade and consumer) of the visitor economy, such as local attractions, trails, tours, and tourism products more generally.

In March 2021 the Ireland-Wales shared statement and joint action plan for 2021 to 2025 was published which sets out the ambitions and plans for the Ireland-Wales relationship in the years ahead.³⁴ The statement recognises that Ireland and Wales share a common maritime story, with their relationship growing from these historic links, rooted in a common heritage and culture and close people-to-people, family, business, academic, cultural and sporting connections. It also recognizes that both nations are bound by strong economic and trading ties with significant levels of export, investment, and tourism between them. The joint high-level Action Plan sets out 6 areas of cooperation, which includes Trade and Tourism and Culture, Language and Heritage.

Of specific relevance to any legacy discussion for Ports, Past and Present, the Action Plan sets **out a commitment to initiate exploratory discussions to foster potential cooperation and collaboration between their respective tourism agencies,** Fáilte Ireland, Tourism Ireland and Visit Wales. It also includes a commitment to support current initiatives and projects which promote awareness and knowledge of our shared history and built heritage. The outcome of these exploratory discussions, along with any future investment secured through Interreg, UKSPF or other sources, will ultimately govern the extent to which the operation is able to realise its full potential within a legacy phase.

³² [Post-EU funding arrangements October 2022 Welsh Parliament Finance Committee](#)

³³ [Department for Levelling Up, Housing & Communities. Interventions list for Wales. 12th April 2022.](#)

³⁴ [Ireland-Wales shared statement and joint action plan 2021 to 2025](#)

6. Conclusion and recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

Ports, Past and Present is a cross-border action funded by the ERDF through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme, managed by WEFO, which aimed to stimulate economic growth by utilising the assets, enhancing the natural and cultural environment and increasing the attractiveness of the coastal communities in the programme area as places to visit. A key focus was support for and diversification of the tourism sector to increase visitor numbers to coastal communities, in particular overseas visitors.

The operation comprises a partnership across higher education and local government and involves a broad range of stakeholders and beneficiaries. The operation aims to increase the capacity of coastal communities to utilise their natural and cultural heritage as a driver to economic and particularly tourist growth.

Covid-19 restrictions have curtailed the efforts to physically engage local communities across the five port towns and as such impacted the progress made across all the work packages. It has also directly impacted on ferry passenger numbers and as such visitor volumes connected to each port. The operation has also been influenced by the progress of Brexit negotiations and more recent the refugee crisis caused by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Feedback from staff and contractors has highlighted satisfaction with the partnership working and governance arrangements for the operation. The Stakeholder Advisory Group was cited as providing valuable and timely guidance and support. With hindsight, greater coordination with other cross-border initiatives should have taken place at an earlier stage to avoid any duplication of effort in the creation of tourism and business networks and to align marketing and communication activities.

Although staff turnover has created challenges to maintaining delivery momentum and partnership working, with the level of turnover associated with the use of fixed-term contracts, the Programme Board have acted to recruit to posts to ensure that the contracted deliverables are achieved where possible.

The participatory approach to delivering the creative connections work packages has provided opportunities for local communities to engage in the creative process to build a sense of pride and ownership. The outputs from this work package have the potential to attract visitors, increase dwell time and improve visitor experience. However, without a clear destination marketing campaign the visibility of these may be low and they will not realise their potential.

Developing the content for the documentary films has enabled the operation to engage and involve a range of stakeholders, supported by extensive research by the academic teams at University College Cork and Aberystwyth University as well as the Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies in Wales.

The Port Fest Events have provided opportunities to showcase the work of the operation in covering and promoting tourism in the previously underappreciated ports. Opportunities to integrate and embed the work of the operation with other cultural festivals and events has also been realised.

A total of 90 events and activities have been delivered by the operation, which has engaged at least 14,806 audience members and participants. Collectively they demonstrate the creative diversity of the operation and its resultant wide appeal. They have been used to generate connections, explore collaboration opportunities, gather insight and data to inform creative and academic outputs and build momentum to raise the profile of the port stories. Those attending the events and activities agreed that their experiences had positively affected their sense of place and local identity and made them feel more connected to the other coastal port communities in the Irish Sea.

The creation of a self-sustaining tourism network was one of the key deliverables for the operation. Whilst attendances at regular networking events have so far been lower than hoped for, they do form part of a longer-term activity to connect and activate local businesses to support a process of raising the profile of the ports and attracting tourism. There are currently 40 network members across the 5 ports.

Feedback from some stakeholders has highlighted wider, external influences that impact on the ability of the ports to realise their potential and build on the momentum delivered by Ports, Past and Present. The most prominent was the current ferry timetables between Wales and Ireland but also the lack of accommodation offer and transport connectivity affecting the ports.

Delivery of Ports, Past and Present helped to bring groups together, raise visibility and awareness of the respective town's or port's heritage and highlighted its ongoing potential to deliver positive social and economic outcomes. Feedback from a wide range of stakeholders demonstrates strong momentum to support any legacy activity across the five ports beyond the close of the current operation and a desire to establish a legacy vehicle to build on or sustain the momentum achieved through its delivery to date.

Realising the potential for the history, heritage and connections between the five ports to contribute to future growth in visitor numbers and the tourism economy requires many of the outputs of the operation to be taken-up, viewed, reused and repurposed. There is a danger that without coordination there will be unnecessary duplication of effort across the Interreg cross-border projects and opportunities for alignment will be missed.

There is also a need for maritime development bodies and transport ministries to compel port and ferry sectors to engage in community development initiatives in and around the Irish Sea ports on which they depend.

The future funding position is also unclear given each nation will now proceed with different funding regimes. However, in principle, the aspirations and objectives of the operation continue to align with those of both Interreg and UKSPF. The Ireland-Wales shared statement and joint action plan for 2021 to 2025 sets out 6 areas of cooperation, which includes Trade and Tourism and Culture, Language and Heritage and a commitment to initiate exploratory discussions to foster potential cooperation and collaboration between their respective tourism agencies. This has direct relevance for the legacy of Ports, Past and Present and should be used as a hook for any legacy conversations.

6.2 Recommendations

A small number of recommendations are provided below for consideration by the Programme Board.

1. Assess options and funding to establish a legacy vehicle to build on the momentum developed by the operation across the five ports.
2. Consider resourcing a destination marketing campaign which draws on the creative output and stories captured by the operation and uses them to promote the ports as destinations.
3. Connect the Tourism Networks more explicitly to respective DMOs, tour operators and local business bodies to explore opportunities and barriers to driving visitor numbers and dwell time across the ports.
4. Ensure that opportunities to embed heritage and the work of Ports, Past and Present into future capital programmes across each of the ports are realised and assess the potential to include meaningful Corporate Social Responsibility elements in future contracts with port and ferry companies to address the lack of voluntary engagement from the commercial sectors with the Irish Sea Port communities.

Appendices

Evaluation of the Ports, Past and Present Project

Discussion Guide for interviews with staff and contractor

The logo for Wavehill, consisting of the word "wavehill" in white lowercase letters on a dark green rectangular background.

This document

First of all, thank you for agreeing to be interviewed.

This is a guide for the discussion that we would like to undertake with you as part of the above evaluation. We would be grateful if you can find a few minutes to read the guide in advance as it includes some background information about the evaluation and also a list of questions that we would like to discuss with you. This discussion guide is however exactly that - a *guide* to the issues that we would like to explore during the meeting. We would, of course, be happy to talk about any other issues which you feel are relevant.

Wavehill are undertaking the evaluation on behalf of the Ports Past and Present Project. The evaluation is now moving into its final phase which is focused on the lessons learnt during the delivery, what has been achieved and the legacy of the project.

People taking part in these interviews have been chosen in consultation with the project management. Participation is voluntary. You can decide to not take part before or during the interview and can choose to not answer certain questions if you prefer.

Any personal information collected as part of the interview is kept confidential. Your answers will help inform our understanding of how the project has been delivered, its achievements and its legacy. Reports produced from any analysis will be presented to the project management, but these will not identify any individuals.

Your personal data is deleted within 6 weeks of the end of the project, projected to be July 2023. Your answers to the interview questions are linked anonymously to other data sources for non-commercial research purposes only, unless you ask for this linkage to not take place. The anonymised data is held securely and is only ever used for non-commercial research purposes. We do not share or use your information for commercial or marketing purposes.

If you have any concerns about how your data has been handled, you can lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office who is the independent regulator for data protection. You can contact the Information Commissioner's Office on 01625 545 745 or 0303 123 1113, via the website www.ico.gov.uk, or write to: Information Commissioner, Wycliffe House, Water Lane, Wilmslow, Cheshire, SK9 5AF.

Some background

The evaluation will consider two main issues:

- Outcomes – what has the project achieved? What has been the impact of the project?
- Process – how has the project been delivered? What has been learned? What could be improved?

We anticipate that the interview should take no longer than 30-45 minutes depending of course on how much you have to say. As you can appreciate, we will be interviewing a wide range of people as part of the evaluation. Accordingly, some of the questions listed may not be applicable to you; we will of course focus on those questions which are relevant to you.

Confidentiality

The data collected will be stored securely on our (Wavehill's) systems until July 2023. Any comments that you make will be confidential and the information you provide will only be used for the purposes of this evaluation. Comments that you make will not be attributed to you. This means it will be impossible for anyone to identify you from any published reports because information will be anonymised.

It is also important to note that the team undertaking the evaluation do not work for UCC or any of the organisations that are involved in the Ports Past and Present Project or funding of this project. This is an *independent* evaluation

Are you happy to continue with the interview? Yes/no (if no end survey) Please note you can withdraw your consent at any time during the interview.

Consent given? (tick box)

1. As an introduction, can you please introduce your role as it relates to the Ports Past and Present Project?

Delivery

2. What have been the strengths of the project from a delivery perspective?
3. What have been the weaknesses of the project from a delivery perspective?
4. Are there any other 'lessons learnt' that you would highlight?
5. Have there been any 'external factors' that have affected the delivery of the project? Economic conditions and the Covid-19 pandemic are obvious examples of external factors that can influence the delivery of a project. If there have, what are they and how have they impacted on delivery?

Working in partnership

6. How has the project worked with other projects or organisations in the areas where the project is active/in your field of work?
How about the partnership working between delivery partners and/or contractors within the project?

Impact and legacy

7. What, in your opinion, will be the impact of the Ports, Past and Present project?
 - a. What do you think the legacy of the project will be i.e. what are likely to be the long-term outcomes and impacts of the project?
 - b. What sources of data would evidence this impact?

Final thoughts

9. Do you have anything to add on an issue we've discussed, or would you like to raise an issue we have not discussed?

Evaluation of the Ports, Past and Present Project

Discussion Guide for interviews with key stakeholders

The logo for Wavehill, consisting of the word "wavehill" in white lowercase letters on a dark green rectangular background.

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed for the Ports, Past and Present Project. The Ports, Past and Present project explores the history and cultures of the five port areas of Dublin and Rosslare in Ireland, and Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock in Wales, and is led by University College Cork (UCC), in partnership with Aberystwyth University, The Centre for Advanced Welsh and Wexford County Council. The project management team has commissioned Wavehill to undertake an evaluation of the project.

During its delivery the project will promote each town's heritage to the public, both within the coastal communities themselves and to the visiting public, and it will shape and inform the long-term heritage tourism strategies of the five port communities and their surrounding areas. The project is being funded by the European Regional Development Fund through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme and is running from May 2019 to April 2023.

This is a guide for the discussion that we would like to undertake with you as part of the above evaluation. It includes some background information about the evaluation and also a list of questions that we would like to discuss with you in relation to the data capture sheets submitted as part of this programme. This discussion guide is however exactly that - a *guide* to help shape our discussions during the meeting. We would, of course, be happy to discuss any other issues which you feel are relevant.

People taking part in these interviews have been chosen in consultation with the project management. Participation is voluntary. You can decide to not take part before or during the interview and can choose to not answer certain questions if you prefer. Any personal information collected as part of the interview is kept confidential. Your answers will help inform our understanding of the project and our development of an appropriate evaluation framework and theory of change. Reports produced from any analysis will be presented to the project management, but these will not identify any individuals.

Your personal data is deleted within 6 weeks of the end of the project, projected to be July 2023. Your answers to the interview questions are linked anonymously to other data sources for non-commercial research purposes only, unless you ask for this linkage to not take place. The anonymised data is held securely and is only ever used for non-commercial research purposes. We do not share or use your information for commercial or marketing purposes.

If you have any concerns about how your data has been handled, you can lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office who is the independent regulator for data protection. You can contact the Information Commissioner's Office on 01625 545 745 or 0303 123 1113, via the website www.ico.gov.uk, or write to: Information Commissioner, Wycliff House, Water Lane, Wilmslow, Cheshire, SK9 5AF.

Confidentiality

The data collected will be stored securely on our (Wavehill's) systems until July 2023. Any comments that you make will be confidential and the information you provide will only be used for the purposes of this evaluation. Comments that you make will not be attributed to you. This means it will be impossible for anyone to identify you from any published reports because information will be anonymised.

It is also important to note that the team undertaking the evaluation do not work for UCC or any of the organisations that are involved in the Ports Past and Present Project or funding of this project. This is an *independent* evaluation.

Are you happy to continue with the interview? Yes/no (if no end survey) Please note you can withdraw your consent at any time during the interview.

We enable our team to review and analyse the content of these interviews we may ask if these can be recorded. Are you happy for this interview to be recorded? Yes/no

Discussion Points

1. Could you give me a brief introduction of yourself and your organisation – e.g. location, sector, role, etc.
2. Have you had any involvement in the Ports, Past and Present project? If so, in what capacity?
3. How important is the town(s) or port's heritage in your area/region? Please explain your answer.
4. Has there been a change in the amount of time tourists spend in your town in general over the last year? If so, please explain that change.
5. If you've identified a change above, is there any particular reason(s) for the change?
6. What have you heard about the Ports, Past and Present project? How would you describe the project to somebody who hasn't heard about it before?
7. Have you participated in / used (etc.) any of the elements of the programme? What did you think of them? How would you improve them? *List added*
 - a) Network linking those interested in heritage and creative arts on both sides of the Irish Sea, to share ideas through monthly online coffee mornings.
 - b) 'Port Fest' online community events focused on sharing creative and heritage links and knowledge in port towns.
 - c) Community engagement in creative commissions work by project creative group.
 - d) Community engagement in production of project documentary films.
 - e) Online heritage stories relating to the port towns, co-created by the project team and community.
 - f) Free mobile app available to tourists to use and which communities can access and develop.
 - g) Professional Tourism Network linking tourism professionals and tourism-related businesses on both sides of the Irish Sea, sharing opportunities for collaboration and learning skills.
 - h) Workshops aimed at helping tourism professionals and businesses to make targeted use of social media and best practice in the development of heritage-related tourism.
 - i) New and original creative works to be displayed in the ports in the cross-maritime area. (Exhibitions and permanent display in 2022-3).
 - j) Publication showing the creative engagements of the project's creative practitioner group.
 - k) Non-fiction films on the history and heritage of the 5 port towns and 3 sea crossings that will help to encourage tourists to visit the port towns.
 - l) Film screenings on ferries, in port terminals and in local communities.
 - m) Signage on display in the port centres to promote online heritage stories and the heritage app.
 - n)
8. What difference do you think the Ports, Past and Present project has made to date?

9. What difference do you think the materials produced by the Ports, Past and Present project will make going forward?
10. What are the key steps that need to be taken to ensure the legacy of the programme?
11. Are there any other comments you'd like to make about the Ports, Past and Present project, or would you like to raise an issue we have not discussed?

Evaluation of the Ports, Past and Present Project

Online Stakeholders Survey (2023)

The Ports, Past and Present (PPP) project is led by University College Cork (UCC), in partnership with Aberystwyth University, The Centre for Advanced Welsh and Celtic Studies/Trinity St Davids and Wexford County Council. The project management team has commissioned Wavehill to undertake an evaluation of the project.

The PPP project explores the history and cultures of the five port areas of Dublin and Rosslare in Ireland, and Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock in Wales. During its delivery the project will promote each town's heritage to the public, both within the coastal communities themselves and to the visiting public, and it will shape and inform the long-term heritage tourism strategies of the five port communities and their surrounding areas. The project is being funded by the European Regional Development Fund through the Ireland Wales Co-operation Programme and is running from May 2019 to April 2023.

The information collected during the survey will be shared with UCC and included in a report for UCC, who are required to share this with their funder (the Welsh European Funding Office) and may also publish it publicly on their website or reference it in academic papers. Your comments will not be attributed to you and you will not be named in either the report or published material. Moreover, your participation is completely voluntary and you may end the survey at any point by closing your browser. However your views and experiences are important to help inform the evaluation of this programme.

UCC is the data controller for the research. However, Wavehill will delete any personal data provided during the survey, before it is shared with UCC. UCC will store non-attributed research data for 10 years, in line with their research policy.

For more information on how your data is handled please see our privacy notice [here](#).

By proceeding with this survey you are granting consent to taking part in the research and for your replies to be recorded.

QA: Are you happy to continue with the survey? Please note you can stop completing the questionnaire at any time if you decide you do not want to continue.

- Yes
- No

QB (if no) Thank you for your time. To exit this survey, you can close this tab in your browser.

Q1 Where are you, your business or organisation based?

- Fishguard
- Holyhead
- Dublin Port
- Pembroke Dock
- Rosslare
- National Organisation (Wales)
- National Organisation (Ireland)
- Transnational/International Organisation (i.e. Ferry company)
- Other [please specify] _____

Q2 Which of the following categories best describes your area of work or interest?

- Local community group
- Local history/education group
- Local business – Accommodation/Food and drink
- Local business – Tourism (activities, tours etc)
- Local business – other
- Management or Government body
- Political
- Individual (not a member of any group)
- Other [please specify] _____

Q3 How familiar or aware are you of the town or port's heritage? *If you are a regional or national organisation please answer for the port(s) in your area in general.*

- I know nothing about the town or port's heritage
- I have a little knowledge and understanding of the town or port's heritage (i.e. less than the average person who lives in the town)
- I have a moderate amount of knowledge and understanding of the town or port's heritage (i.e. about the same as the average person who lives in the town)
- I have a lot of knowledge and understanding of the town or port's heritage (i.e. more than the average person who lives in the town)
- I am particularly knowledgeable about the town or port's heritage (i.e. I have a particular or specialist interest in the town or port's heritage)

Q4 How important is the town or port's heritage to your business or organisation? *i.e. is it something that helps with marketing; drawing visitors and customers; contributes to your brand.*

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important
- Not relevant

Q5 Please use this space if you wish to discuss, explain or elaborate on how important the town or port's heritage is to your business.

Q6 Have you seen a change in the amount of time tourists spend in your town in general over the last 12 months?

- Yes – increased
- Yes – decreased
- No – stayed the same
- Don't know

Q7 (If yes above) How much has that change been?

- Substantial
- A small change
- Don't know

Q8 (If yes above) Do you identify any particular reason for the change? If so, please note it below.

Q9 Has there been a change in the importance of heritage to the tourism offer in your town over the last 12 months?

- Yes – increased
- Yes – decreased
- No – stayed the same
- Don't know

Q10 (If yes above) How significant has that change been?

- Substantial
- A small change
- Don't know

Q11 (If yes above) Do you identify any particular reason for the change? If so, please note it below.

Q12 The objectives of the Ports, Past and Present project are:

'To create a new tourism network that links the 5 coastal communities around cultural, natural or heritage tourism; whilst producing a broad range of media aimed to encourage tourists visiting coastal communities and port towns to spend more time and money.' , and

'To explore the cultures of the port areas of Dublin, Rosslare, Holyhead, Fishguard and Pembroke Dock and bring this heritage to public awareness, both within coastal communities and to increase visitor numbers and enhance visitor experiences.'

Q13 On a scale of 1-5 (1=not at all 5=Yes, to a great extent), to what extent do you think this is needed in your area?

- 1 (Not needed at all)
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 (Yes, to a great extent)

Q14 Please could you briefly tell us why you have given that response?

Q15 How much information have you seen or received about the Ports, Past and Present project?

- None at all
- A little
- A moderate amount
- A lot
- A great deal

Q16 Below are some of the things that the Ports, Past and Present project have been working upon. Please let us know to what extent you are aware of and / or have used or taken part each of these:

	Not aware of	Aware of but did not use or take part	Aware of and used or took part
<p>1. Network linking those interested in heritage and creative arts on both sides of the Irish Sea, to share ideas through monthly online coffee mornings.</p> <p>2. 'Port Fest' online community events focused on sharing creative and heritage links and knowledge in port towns.</p> <p>3. Community engagement in creative commissions work by project creative group.</p> <p>4. Community engagement in production of project documentary films.</p> <p>5. Online heritage stories relating to the port towns, co-created by the project team and community.</p> <p>6. Free mobile app available to tourists to use and which communities can access and develop.</p>			

Q17 [If used] How useful have these outputs been to you and/or your organisation?

LIST ASPECTS OF THE PROJECT HERE.	Not useful at all	Slightly useful	Reasonably useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
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Q18 (if not aware or not used of the activity in response to the questions above) How interested would you potentially be in these things if you knew a bit more about them?

LIST ASPECTS OF THE PROJECT HERE.	Not at all	Slightly interested	Reasonably interested	Very interested	Extremely interested
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Q19 The Ports, Past and Present project is currently delivering seven more programmes. Again, please let us know to what extent you are aware of and / or have used or taken part in each of these:

	Not aware of	Aware of but did not use or take part	Aware of and used or took part
<p>1. Professional Tourism Network linking tourism professionals and tourism-related businesses on both sides of the Irish Sea, sharing opportunities for collaboration and learning skills.</p> <p>2. Workshops aimed at helping tourism professionals and businesses to make targeted use of social media and best practice in the development of heritage-related tourism.</p> <p>3. New and original creative works to be displayed in the ports in the cross-maritime area. (Exhibitions and permanent display in 2022-3).</p> <p>4. Publication showing the creative engagements of the project's creative practitioner group.</p> <p>5. Non-fiction films on the history and heritage of the 5 port towns and 3 sea crossings that will help to encourage tourists to visit the port towns.</p> <p>6. Film screenings on ferries, in port terminals and in local communities.</p> <p>7. Signage on display in the port centres to promote online heritage stories and the heritage app.</p>			

Q20 [If used] How useful have these outputs been to you and/or your organisation?

LIST ASPECTS OF THE PROJECT HERE.	Not useful at all	Slightly useful	Reasonably useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
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Q21 (if not aware of or not used the activity in response to the questions above) How interested would you potentially be in these things if you knew a bit more about them?

LIST ASPECTS OF THE PROJECT HERE.	Not at all	Slightly interested	Reasonably interested	Very interested	Extremely interested
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Q22 Finally, we would like to do a follow up consultation with local stakeholders involved in the project. Would you be interested in taking part in a follow up interview?

y/n

Q23 If so, please provide your contact details below.

Contact us

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wavehill@wavehill.com

wavehill.com

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